

Middle East University

Faculty of Business

The Relationship between Capital Adequacy Ratio and Profitability in the Financial
Markets: A Study on the Lebanese Banking Sector 2004-2013

A Thesis

Presented in Partial Fulfillment

Of the Requirements for the degree

Master of Business Administration

by

Younna Michael Issa

September 2014

Thesis Abstract

Master of Business Administration

Middle East University

Faculty of Business Administration

Title: THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN CAPITAL ADEQUACY RATIO AND PROFITABILITY IN THE FINANCIAL MARKET: A STUDY IN THE LEBANESE BANKING SECTOR 2004-2013

Researcher: Youmna Michael Issa

Advisor: Dr. Paul Abboud, PhD

Date Completed: September, 2014

The Lebanese banking sector has been known by its resiliency and stability. One of the most important key marks of this resiliency is the limited repercussions the 2008 financial crisis has had on the banking sector in Lebanon.

Banque du Liban has always been keen to implement local and international rules and regulations in order for it to maintain and increase this stability. Highly capitalized banks are a major objective that the central banks had to achieve. The current Capital Adequacy Ratio in the

Lebanese banking sector stands at a higher rate than the minimum required by Basel Committee on Banking Supervision.

High capital in a certain bank increases the trust given by depositors and lenders. On the other side, the bank will be exposed at paying opportunity costs. The degree of opportunity cost differs depending on the size of the bank, the environment where it operates as well as the current level Capital Adequacy ratio and where it stands from the optimal Capital Adequacy Ratio.

This paper will examine the repercussion on the profitability of an additional increase in the current Capital Adequacy Ratio for three Alfa banks in the Lebanese banking sector. In addition, it will describe the changes in correlation across the implementation of Basel I, II and III between Capital Adequacy ratio, Cost of Income and profitability ratios.

It will conclude that an increase in the Capital Adequacy Ratio will have negative effects on the profitability of the Lebanese banking sector.

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN CAPITAL ADEQUACY RATIO AND
PROFITABILITY IN THE FINANCIAL MARKET: A STUDY IN THE LEBANESE
BANKING SECTOR 2004-2013

A Thesis

Presented in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements for the Degree of Masters of
Business Administration

by

Youmna Michel Issa

APPROVAL BY THE COMMITTEE:

Paul Abboud, Ph.D., Adviser

Denny Rumambi, Ph.D., Reader

Patrizia Hongisto., Faculty Dean

Date of Approval

Dedication

To the one who sacrificed.....

To the one who loved unconditionally.....

To the reason that made me become who I am.....

To the continuous support, love and respect.....

To my father I dedicate this work.....

Acknowledgment

I would like to thank

My small family, my mother sisters and brothers, I am grateful and lucky to have such support in my life.

Dr. Paul Abboud, my advisor, for making me to discover my passion to the financial world and for making this work comes true.

Mr. Alexander Nemer who converted the invisible into visible, for all the support he provided me with.

Mrs. Sana Issa along with Dr. John Issa who both played the greatest motiv behind this accomplishment.

LIST OF FIGURES

1. Audi Bank CAR, COI, ROCE, ROAA
2. BLOM Bank CAR, COI, ROCE, ROAA
3. Byblos Bank CAR, COI, ROCE, ROAA
4. CAR Trend for Audi, Byblos and BLOM banks 2004-2013
5. COI Trend for Audi, Byblos and BLOM banks; 2004-2013
6. ROAA Trend for Audi, Byblos and BLOM banks; 2004-2013
7. ROCE Trend for Audi, Byblos and BLOM banks; 2004-2013
8. Audi Bank Correlations between Variables
9. BLOM Bank Correlations between Variables
10. Byblos Bank Correlations between Variables

TABLE OF CONTENT

LIST OF FIGURES	xii
LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS.....	xvii
INTRODUCTION	7
Statement of the Problem	10
Hypotheses	11
Purpose of the study	11
Objectives of the study.....	12
Limitation of the Study	12
REVIEW OF LITERATURE	13
Banking Sector and its Importance	13
Basel Committee on Banking Supervision	18
Basel III	20
Important Changes among Basel I, II and III.....	21
Capital Adequacy Ratio Qualitative Changes	21
Tier Components	24
Deductions.....	25
Risk Definition and Risk Modes	27
Risk Definition	27
Risk Calculations Approaches	28

Credit Risk.....	28
Operational Risk.....	28
Market Risk.....	29
Counterparty Risk.....	29
Other Types of risk.....	30
Capital Adequacy Ratio Formula Changes.....	31
Profitability of Banks.....	32
CAMEL Model.....	32
Capital Adequacy and profitability.....	33
Asset Quality and Profitability.....	33
Liquidity and Profitability.....	34
Diversification of Income and Profitability.....	35
Internal Factors Affecting Profitability.....	35
External Factors Affecting Profitability.....	37
Measurement of Bank Profitability.....	38
Financial Crisis.....	39
Classification of Financial Crisis.....	39
The 2008 Financial Crisis.....	41
Factors Affecting Capital Adequacy Ratio Performance.....	44
Capital Adequacy Ratio and Pro cyclical Problem.....	44
Capital Requirement and Risk Problem.....	47
Capital Adequacy Ratio and Profitability.....	48

Lebanese Financial Market and BCBS Implementation	51
Lebanese Financial Sector Features	51
Banking Efficiency.....	54
Banking Efficiency Definition.....	54
Relationship between Cost of Income and Profitability	55
RESEARCH METHODOLOGY	58
Instruments	59
Research Questions and CAR Performance.....	60
Data Collection and Analysis	64
Program used Description	66
Correlation Description	67
Qualitative Data Collection.....	68
DATA ANALYSIS.....	70
Graph Description	70
Performance by Bank	70
Ratio Comparison between Banks	73
Correlation Description	75
Changes of Correlations through Basel I, II and III.....	76
Analysis of the Results.....	80
Analysis on Changes in Correlations	82
Bank Performance and Scenario Analysis	84
Optimal Capital Adequacy Ratio	88

CONCLUSION.....	95
Recommendations.....	96
APPENDIX A.....	98
APPENDIX B.....	108
REFERENCES	109

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

BCBS Basel Committee on Banking Supervision

BCC Banking Control Commission

CAR Capital Adequacy Ratio

COI Cost of Income

ROCE Return on Common Equity

ROAE Return on Average Equity

ROAA Return on Average Assets

MENA Middle East and North Africa

IMF International Monetary Fund

S&L Saving and Loans

BDL Banque Du Liban

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

According to the Basel Committee Basel Supervision (BCBS, 2013) the recommendations to implement a uniformed Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) had one important objective. This objective was to promote a more resilient global banking sector and that is by reforming and promoting new capital and liquidity rules. This is due to the important role banks play in the economy of a certain country. This paper will explore the relationship of implementing a high CAR and the profitability ratios in the Lebanese banking sector. 2004 till 2013.

The breakdown of the Breton woods, the withdrawal of the banking license of Bankhaus Herstatt's and the close up of Franklin National Bank of New York led the central bank governor of the G10 countries to established a committee. Those failures were due to tremendous foreign exchange loss, and well as to other financial disagreements. The committee, later on named Basel Committee on Banking Supervision, aimed to create and develop financial regulations and ways to implement them in order for it to enhance global financial stability (*Balthazar, 2006*)

The committee started its first meeting in 1975 with the G10 countries and in 2009 it expanded its membership to include 27 jurisdictions (*Balthazar, 2006*). Below is a brief summary of the major meeting:

Basel I

The Latin American debit crises increased the committee awareness to raise concerns in the capital adequacy. In 1988, the “*Basel Capital Accord*” was released. It called for a minimal

capital ratio of capital to risk weighted assets of 8% to be implemented in 1992. In 1996, the 1988 accord was reviewed and the “*Market Risk Amendment to the Capital Accord*” was published (Baltahazar, 2006).

Basel II

In 2004, the “*Revised Capital Framework*” was published and that was after a proposal done by the committee in 1999 for a new capital adequacy framework to replace the Basel Capital Accord. The Revised Capital Framework comprised three pillars and it was set mainly to ameliorate the way regulatory capital requirements reflect underlying risks and to address the risk of the financial innovations that have appeared in recent years.

Basel III

In the financial crisis of the 2008, the banking sector entered to a crisis with high leverage and poor liquidity buffer. The BCBS went conscious about the necessity to redefine rules. The BCBS issued then, the Principles for “*Sound Liquidity Risk Management and Supervision*” in the same month of Lehman Brother’s failure in September 2008.

In November 2010, the governors of the G20 countries endorsed a new minimum capital requirement standard Basel III, International Framework for “*Liquidity Risk Measurement, Standards and Monitoring*”. The minimum CAR is recommended to be 10.5% with 2.5% conversation buffer included. (BIS, 2013).

A study conducted by the International Journal of Applied Economics mentioned that a profitability of a certain bank is positively related to the core capital ratio and the risk- based

capital. However, it is negatively related to the equity capital ratio and the COI ratio (Mathuva, 2009).

Other advocates believed that the application of minimal CAR protect depositors account and help maintain the stability of the financial system. It insures that a certain bank can absorb reasonable losses resulting from different sources of risk (RBN, 2007).

On the other hand, economist argued that implementing required CAR in slowdown economy will decrease the money supply in the market leading to a decrease in the overall economic growth. A negative economic growth will also have a negative impact on bank performance (Hanke, 2012).

Besanko and Spulber argued that a higher CAR may lead to a higher outside equity, which in turn would increase moral hazard because managers will have a decreased stake in their bank (Besanko, et al, 1999). Another study “Optimal Bank Regulation in Boom and recession” conducted by both Lin and Hu, shows that if the moral hazard is very severe and investors are highly risk averse, the increase of the CAR would have a pro-cyclical effect instead of counter-cycle ones especially in the emerging markets. (Lin)

Besanko and Thakor (1992) concluded the positive and the negative correlation between capital requirements and equilibrium loan size and the equilibrium deposit rate (Gorton, 2003).

Stiglitz (2001) believes that if a bank’s policy is to implement higher CAR, the same bank will seek for more risky assets in order for it to offset the cost of funding of capital. Stolz (2002), and Jackson (1999) both argued that effective financial stability in emerging countries would be by creating effective regulatory institutions rather to implement capital adequacy requirement (Barrell, et al, 2006). Kohane (1977), as mentioned by Berger in the Journal of

Finance, showed that capital requirements by themselves can be unsuccessful in controlling bank risk and may even provoke banks to choose riskier assets (Berger, 1995).

Statement of the Problem

The U.S Bank Data between 1985 and 1990s showed a positively related relation between CAR and bank profitability especially on the Return on Equity (Berger, 1995).

On the other side, theories have shown that an inappropriate capital adequacy ratio could have negative repercussions on the profitability of the banking sector.

Once banks get to determine their optimal capital adequacy ratio, there would be a zero relation between capital adequacy ratio and bank's profitability (*Capital and Profitability on Banking: Case from US banks p.31*). This study approves the possibility of the negative relation between the CAR and the bank's profitability

Lebanon's Capital Adequacy Ratio and as recommended by BDL is at 12.2%. Knowing that the Minimum CAR required by Basel III is at 10%, and with an increasing Cost of Income ratio, and a declining growth of profit in the Lebanese banks, more attention was given to CAR instead of Cost of Income Ratio (figure 1) (Najd,2005).

Recent studies in Lebanon have shown that Lebanon has a very high CAR and Cost of income compared to emerging countries, MENA region and the world. In return it has the lowest ROE and ROA in the same area. Lebanese banks are paying an opportunity cost which is by not investing a certain quantity of money and thus, they are decreasing their profitability (Barakat, 2014).

Hypotheses

Research Hypotheses of this research is to show or to prove that there is no significant positive relation between CAR and the profitability of the banks in the Lebanese financial sector. Furthermore, there is an inverse relationship between Cost of Income and profitability, as a result, attesting that the following previously stated hypotheses may be true:

H.1 an increase in the CAR will not necessarily increase bank's profitability. In contrast, it may lead to a decrease in the bank's performance.

H.2 keeping CAR constant, a decrease in the COI will increase bank's profitability especially that CAR and the COI are generally negatively correlated.

H.3 a decrease in both CAR and Cost of income will increase bank's profitability and could be the optimal solution in keeping an efficient banking system

H.4 the profitability in H3 will be higher than the profitability in H2

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study is to show that implementing higher CAR will not increase the profitability in the Lebanese banking sector. Instead, profitability will decrease. On the other hand, a decrease in the COI would have a higher impact on the Lebanese banking industry (Barakat, 2014). A decrease in the COI will increase banks profitability. As a result, a decrease in both CAR and COI will lead to a significant increase in the profitability. This study was not

conducted before in the Lebanese market. That is why it will add more awareness concerning the adoption of Basel III recommendations.

Objectives of the Study

The objective of this thesis is to shed light on the problem that Lebanese banks do not stand at their equilibrium since they are holding neither an optimal CAR nor an optimal COI. A high CAR will be offsetting the expansionary monetary policy as well as negatively affecting the profitability ratio.

Limitation of the Study

Government expenditures, taxation, technological innovations, interest rates and political stability are above few factors that affect banking industry in a certain economy Lebanon has always been known by its rapidly changing macroeconomic environment (Barro, 1996). It was always characterized by its political crisis that led periods of economic and social instabilities.

Another thing is the complexity of the bank transactions and the effects bank components have on each other. That is why the relation between two variables of a certain bank cannot be fully isolated from other influential factors. So that is why it is challenging to measure the exclusive relation between CAR, COI and profitability ratios.

Another limitation of the study is that the changes between variables on the graphs cannot be done since the used formulas in calculating the CAR are not the same for Basel I and Basel II

CHAPTER 2

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Financial Rules and Regulations History

Banking Sector and its Importance

According to Financial Times, a commercial bank is a financial institution that provides services for businesses, organizations and individuals. A commercial bank is defined as a bank which main business is deposit-taking and making loans.

Those banks accept short term and relatively liquid deposits and transform them into longer maturity loans. By this process they generate their profit.

Banks play a major role in allocating a certain country resources, monitoring its companies and industries in addition to providing the market with liquidity as well as risk management services (Laeven, 2005).

There is a strong positive relationship between the welfare of a financial sector and the economic growth of a certain country. There are two main financial systems that have different effects on the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) in different situations. In fact, in a financial stability period and in absence of financial crises, countries with bank-based economy will be

more resilient than economies with market-based economies. The opposite is true during an economic recession or a financial crisis. To illustrate this, a study conducted by the Bank of International Settlements on 41 countries during the 1990s and the 2000s showed that, during financial stability, countries with bank based did not register any GDP loss while market-based economies lost on average 3%.

On the other hand, during financial recession, economies with bank-based economies, will incur an average loss of GDP of 12.5% whereas, the market-based countries will incur a 4.2% of the GDP. That is when a financial crisis is able to handicap a banking sector by itself; the recession will be stricter on bank-based economies (Gambacorta, et al, 2014).

To note that in a market based financial system, the stock market and the economic trend hold most of the financial power. In such a system, the profit of banks is based more on fee services rather than interest from loans. Furthermore, privately owned non-banking financial institutions provide investment services that might compete with the government. On the other side a bank based financial system is tightly regulated by laws set out by the government mainly common law. The economy in the bank based financial system depends to a large extreme on the performance of the banking sector (Trehan, 2008).

As noted before, financial crisis presents a major obstacle in the performance welfare of banks. Financial crisis is manifested at the level of the financial institutions especially at the level of the banking industry. Even though, financial crisis can be generated by non-financial institutions, banks play an important role in the occurrence, conveying and solving the financial crisis (Cecchetti et al, 2009).

The history of the banking sector was characterized by succession of financial crisis followed by implementation of new rules and regulations. For example, the Great Depression in 1929, which lasted over approximately one decade, was due to the crash in the prices of the Dow Jones that went down from \$386 in September 1929 to \$40 in July 1939. This financial crisis has had a negative impact on the overall economy when unemployment rate in 1933 reached 25% and the Gross National Product went down by 30.8% (Smiley, 2008)

At that time, a run occurred. According to the Business Dictionary, a run by definition is a sudden and heavy cash withdrawal by depositors who lost confidence in the viability of a bank, or expect the economy to crash or slow down drastically. At that time many banks were not able to meet the depositors request and they went insolvent. According to the previously mentioned reference, a bank goes insolvent when its liabilities exceed the value of owned assets.

As a reaction to this crisis, Senator Stegal suggested the creation of the Federal Deposit Insurance Company (FDIC) which is a financial institution that provides governmental guarantees to the creditors of banks. This step was to prevent from occurrence of runs or at least to minimize their effects. Another thing was the creation of what is called the “Chinese Wall” that was proposed by Senator Glass that obliged banks to decide on their business line activities. As a result, banks were split between commercial and investment banks (Balthazar, 2006).

In 1944, and after the WWII, European financials decided that the floating system, where the prices of the currency were determined exclusively based on the supply and demand of that currency, was one of the major reasons for the economic collapse at that time. So, they created what was called the “*Bretton Woods*” in which the USD was fixed against the gold (\$35 per

ounce) and all other currencies were to be exchanged against the USD within a floating margin of one 1%. In addition of that, the International Monetary Fund (IMF) was created to rule this new system (Baltahzar, 2006).

In 1973, the “*Bretton Woods*” system repercussions started to appear. Because all currencies were fixed against the USD, and because most international payments were done through that currency, large quantities of USD have had to be injected in the market. So the reserves of USD owned by foreign countries increased from 12.6 B in 1950 to 53.4B in 1970. While the US Gold reserves went down from 20B till 10B in the same period (Balthazar, 2006).

In this same year, the “*Bretton Woods*” system failed. As a result, the European Commission developed a new directive, the “National Treatment” principle. This new directive obliged all banks to abide by the same rule of the country where they operate even if their head office was located in another country (Balthazare, 2006).

When the crisis of the Savings and Loans(S&L) started in the 1980, the economic environment got instable environment. In the 70s, the effective interest rate turned to be 9% while the inflation was around 12% and the government bonds at 11%. In this period, the market experienced interest rates thrifths disintermediation. Where market interest rises above government the maximum sat interest rates. This decreased trust by depositors, as a result, a run occurred (Laughlin, 1990). To compensate their costly funding, Banks started to invest in riskier assets such as junk bonds, construction and development.

As a result, the US regulators introduced for the first time the concept of capital ratio and the leverage ratio on the capital (Balthzar, 2006). Where, according to the Financial Times,

leverage ratio describes the amount of equity in comparison to debt or the amount of earnings in comparison to debt.

The US International Lending and Supervisory Act, which is a law or an act of the FDIC that aims to enhance economic stability in the US and other nations (FDIC), required the CAR to be 5.5% of all types of banks. However, the Rumasa crisis hit Spain even though the Spanish banking system was well regulated. However, because entrepreneurs got license without having banking experience, the results between 1978 and 1983 were disastrous since more than 50 banks at that time were hit by the crisis (Balthazar, 2006).

To solve this issue, survived banks absorbed the losses through their existing capital and received money from the government others were nationalized.

In addition of the above-mentioned crisis, financial crisis never stopped to occur. Continental Illinois which was the 7th largest American bank went bankrupt after it had concentrated his investment only in the energy industry and the state geographic area. There were 2,999 banks that had deposits in Continental Illinois which 179 out of them would go bankrupt if Continental Illinois were bankrupt. So, Regulators injected 2.2 billion to the bank and a credit of 5.3 billion was granted by a group of 24 major US banks (Balthazar, 2006).

During the crash on the stock exchange in the 1987, the Dow Jones, CAC40 and Nikkei lost respectively 22.6%, 9.5% and 14.9%, the governors of the G10 countries recognized the urge of issuing unified rules and regulation to be adopted by all countries. Those rules were done through the committee that is nowadays called the Basel Committee on Banking Supervision

(BCBS). It held its meeting at the “Bank for International Settlement” in Basel Switzerland (Balthazar, 2006).

Basel Committee on Banking Supervision

In 1974, representative from the central banks of the G10 countries, Belgium, Canada, France, Germany, Italy, Japan, Netherlands, Sweden, the United Kingdom and the US in addition to Switzerland and Luxembourg established the BCBS; the committee does not have any legal force. However; it aimed to enhance the quality of the worldwide banking sector supervision and to set regulations that would regularize the cooperation between countries. The committee expanded its members to include 20 countries nowadays (Alessi, 2012). BCBS main meetings are as follow:

Basel 1

As previously mentioned, the committee main objectives were mainly to implement a multinational accord that will increase the quality of the banking sector. That was to override competitiveness arising from differences in the minimal capital requirements between countries.

After the committee took corrective actions on its previously published papers in the 1987, they published the *Basel 1988 Accord* or the 1988 accord that was approved by all members and released to the banks in the same year. The accord required a minimal CAR of 8% to be implemented in 1992. By September 1993, all G10 countries were fully compliant with the Basel Accord (BCBS, 2013).

Having an objective to constantly improve its rules regulations, the BCBS issued successive amendments following the 1998 Accord. In November 1991, the committee gave a more precise definition to general provisions that follows a bad debt and that can be a component in the calculation of the CAR. By definition, according to the BIS, provisions are set aside as a buffer against credit losses. They are positively to the quality of the credits and the loan/asset ratio. A high loan/asset ratio means a low quality of credit implying a high non-performing loan ratio (Packer, 2012). In April 1995, the committee amended the capital accord in order to identify the bank repercussion resulting from the exposure of a certain bank in the derivative market (BCBS, 2013).

In 1996, in order to integrate with the capital accord the risk arising from market exposure due to banks investment in equities, foreign exchange and other marketable securities, the committee published the “*Market Risk Amendment to the Capital Accord*” (BCBS, 2013).

In 2004, the committee issued the “*Revised Capital Framework*” that replaced the 1988 Accord. The new released framework was mainly amended to set for new principles of calculation of the CAR as well as to the definition of the quality of capital that should be included in the calculations. In addition, three pillars were introduced:

- Pillar I: To develop and expand the rules set in the 1988 accord
- Pillar II: To Review of capital adequacy ratio supervisory and internal reviews
- Pillar III: To promote the usage of disclosures to increase market discipline

G10 countries as well as other non-member countries decided to adopt the Revised Capital Framework. However, it was a challenging task and that is due to differences in countries and between the bank and its host.

This was mainly due to the exposure of each country to different types of risk and in the different approaches in risk evaluation those countries adopt. In order to increase the degree of cooperation between home and host supervisors and in order to guide, share and allocate information, the BCBS addressed those issues in the “*Advanced Measurement Approaches*” respectively in 2006 and 2007 (BCBS, 2013).

Basel III

During the financial crisis of the 2008, the banking sector was inadequately capitalized and lacked sound governance and risk management. Credit was growing at an increasing rate in addition to the inappropriate pricing of credit and liquidity risks. In response to the previously mentioned reasons, the BCBS issued the “Principles for Sound Liquidity Risk Management and Supervision” in July 2009 the same month of collapse of Lehman Brothers.

In September 2010, the committee announced an increase in the worldwide adequacy ratio. The ratio was set at 10.5%. In December 2010, the BSBC published the “*International Framework for Liquidity, Risk Measurement, Standards and Monitoring*” in which the three pillars of Basel II were revised by the committee (BCBS, 2013).

Important Changes among Basel I, II and III

As previously mentioned, BCBS aimed to ameliorate the banking sector and that was either through the issuance of new regulations or the amendments of already existing ones.

In this section, the changes in the qualitative components of capital held in the calculation of the CAR, the different newly introduced types of risk banks would be exposed to and the models to calculate the intensity of each type of risk.

Capital Adequacy Ratio Qualitative Changes

According to Financial Times, CAR is one measure of a bank financial strength. It is the ratio of a certain bank capital divided by its weighted risk assets. It is a measurement of the capability of a bank to absorb potential losses coming from different types of risks.

In Basel I, the CAR was set at a level of 8%. It was calculated by dividing tier 1 and tier 2 over the risk weighted assets. Assets are classified into four categories. To each category was assigned a conversion rate depending on the riskiness of the asset category (Söderberg, 2011). In order to calculate the credit risk or what is called the risk weighted assets, the loans made to government and central banks, Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) banks and securities firms, residential mortgages-fully secured, retail lending and corporate and commercial real estate were given respectively the following conversion rates 0%, 20%, 50%, 100% and 100% (Thun, 2011).

The calculations of CAR was criticized by both regulatory and bankers. In fact regulatory argued that adoption of the CAR will lead banks to increase the capital arbitrage; whereas,

bankers thought that it will increase the discrepancy between regulatory and economic capital (Thun, 2011). Where regulatory capital is the minimum capital required by the BCBS, the economic capital is the capital chosen by shareholders without taking into consideration the minimum required (Repullo, 2007).

As mentioned above, the BSBC introduced three pillars. The first pillar redefined the calculations of the quality of the capital that shall be used in the CAR calculations. The next section will introduce the new types of risk defined as well as new models to adopt upon calculations of risk (Thun, 2011).

In 1996, upon the introduction of the Market Risk Amendment to the Capital Accord

The new CAR added to the previously defined denominator the market risk capital. The minimal capital adequacy ratio was kept at the 8% level. Tier 3 was only used to offset the potential losses arising from market risk (BSBC, 2004).

Basel II, the operation risk was added to the denominator of the CAR in addition to new approaches in calculating the credit risk.

In Basel III, was characterized by both quantitative and qualitative changes in the CAR calculations. Below are the main changes between Basel II and Basel III:

- Increase of the Tier 1 ratio from 4 to 6% at the end of January 2015.
- Common stock equity should represent 82.3% from tier 1
- A capital conservation buffer which is set at 2.5% and will only be used to absorb losses due to financial distress. The capital conservation buffer ratio level is included in the Tier

1 ratio so the total tier 1 ratio will come to 8.5% level in the end of January 2015 (BCBS, 2011). The capital conservation buffer is used for macro prudential issues. In fact, it should be built in periods of excess growth. One way to increase this capital is through a decrease in the shareholder's dividends payment (Lekatis, 2011).

- A countercyclical conservation buffer that ranges between 0 to 2.5% of the risk weighted assets depending on the economic situation of the country (BCBS, 2011).

The above-mentioned changes have had the following objectives: raise both the quality and the quantity of tier 1 capital, simplify and reduce tier 2 capital, harmonize the regulatory amendments, implement stricter criteria for each tier components. As a result, the major component of the tier 1 that shall be dominated is the common equity. Common equity includes common shares and retained earnings. The additional tier 1 will remain the same. On the other side, the Gone-concern or the tier 2 capital will be used to give guarantee to depositors and creditor that their capital will be paid back in case the bank failed. Tier 2 should also be used to prevent the bank from becoming insolvent (Auer, 2012).

To note that banks should try to build the capital conservation buffer in good times. It is used to make sure that the bank is able to absorb losses resulting from stress periods. Those stress periods can last for years. In case the bank was not able to meet the minimum requirement of capital conservation buffer, the CET1 will be exposed to dividends payments constrains. In fact, dividends and bonus payments, shares repurchase and amounts paid up in capital repayments would have to be added to CET1.

On the other hand, countercyclical capital buffer will be used to protect the banking sector and the macro economy from the boost of excess credit growth and from bank's exposure to different

types of risks arising from financial disabilities. Similar to capital conservation buffer, the countercyclical capital buffer should be built up in periods of excessive credit growth and used in periods of economic downturn. In case banks failed to meet the minimal required countercyclical capital buffer, the committee that is responsible for the countercyclical capital buffer settings should set another guide *“based on a deviation of the ratio of credit-to-GDP from its long-term trend on quarterly basis”* (Auer, 2012).

Tier Components

Tier 1 is the sum of the Core Capital Tier 1 or the Common Equity Tier1 (CET1) and the additional Tier 1.

- The Core Capital Tier 1 or Common Equity Tier includes:

Common shares issued by the bank, Stock surplus, retained earnings, accumulated comprehensive income, and common shares issued by consolidated subsidiaries of the bank and held by third parties. (BCBS, 2010)

- The additional Tier 1 or core capital consists of:
 - Common shares paid in capital and capital allocation
 - Preferred non-cumulative perpetual preferred shares
 - Premiums
 - Cash contribution
 - Retained earnings
- Tier 2 or the supplementary capital consists of:

- Subordinated loans and notes, fully paid, unsecured with a maturity of more than five years
- Revaluation of fixed assets
- Preferred stocks that do not match tier 1 criteria
- Tier 3 or Additional supplementary capital consists of:
- Subordinated loans or notes fully paid with a maturity of more than 2 years (Nehme, 2011)

Deductions

In order to get to the optimal qualitative capital, the BSBC decided some adjustments or deductions. Below, are mentioned the final deduction as recommended by Basel III (Auer, 2012).

- Assets securitization: When there is an increase in equity or fund element as a result of applying the Generally Accepted Accounting Standards.
- Liability changes and cash flow hedges: Changes that resulted from a change in the credit standing of an institution. Gains or losses that are reported at fair value, but that are not valid at fair value.
- Adjustments of value: Any unneeded change in value due to the application of the valuation specified by the BCBS.
- Fair value of unrealized gain or losses: banks should not adjust their balance sheet for unrealized gains or losses reported at their fair value.
- Deductions on Tier 1 Common Equity

Below are mentioned the elements that shall be deducted from the Tier 1 Common

Equity:

- Deferred tax assets
- Negative expected losses
- Benefit pension fund assets
- Direct and indirect holding of Tier 1 common equity
- Reciprocal cross holding on Tier 1 common equity
- Non-significant and insignificant investments in relevant entities
- Amount that exceed additional Tier 1 capital
- Tax charge

Asset deferred taxes and significant investment in relevant entity shall not be deducted from CET1 if the total of those items after adjustment is equal or less than 15%. In this case, the deferred taxes are those that depend on future probability of occurrence and that result from current differences.

- Deductions from Additional Tier 1 capital
 - Direct and indirect holding of additional tier 1 items
 - Items of entities with reciprocal cross holding
 - Non- significant and significant investments in relevant entities
 - Amount that exceeds Tier 2 Capital
- Tax charge
- Deduction from Tier 2 Capital

- Direct and indirect holding of Tier 2 items:
- Items of entities with reciprocal cross holding:
- Significant and non-significant investments in relevant entities:

Risk Definition and Risk Modes

Risk Definition

In Basel II, the committee gave more attention to the importance of risk effects on the banking sector performance. So the actual calculation of the CAR was closely related to the risk (Thun, 2011). The first pillar of Basel II actually included three types of risks defined below according to Moody's Analytics:

- Credit Risk: arises from the potential that an obligor is either unwilling to perform on an obligation or its ability to perform such obligation is impaired resulting in economic loss to the bank.
- Market Risk: is the risk that the value of the bank's on-and off-balance sheet positions will be adversely affected by movement in market rates or prices, resulting in a loss to earnings or capital
- Operational Risk: is the risk of loss resulting from inadequate or failed internal processes, people and systems, or from external events.

On the other hand the calculations of the above mentioned risk had different ways of calculations.

The Credit risk was used to calculate the CAR in Basel I. The amendment of Basel I in 1996 introduced the market risk while the operational risk was introduced in Basel II.

Risk Calculations Approaches

Credit Risk

As mentioned earlier, Basel I set fixed conversion rates to calculate Credit Risk. However, In Basel II, four models were introduced:

- Simplified standardized approach that relies on export credit agencies 'rating
- Standardized approach that relies on rating agencies
- Foundation internal rating based approached that relies partially on bank's internal ratings of credit risk as well as on approvals of supervisory committees
- Advanced internal rating-based agency that relies totally on bank's internal ratings of credit
- risk as well as on approvals of supervisory committees

Operational Risk

The calculations of the Operational Risk did not change across Basel I, II and III. Every bank had to choose one approach to calculate this type of risk.

- Basic indicator approach that implies a bank to keep a fixed percentage of its capital α which equals 15% of its three years last profit.
- Standardized Measurement Approach that relies on internal assessment of operation risk based on the working units and bank's provided services. The percentage of capital in reserve should rely between 12 and 18%.
- Advanced Measurement Approach relies on bank's policy to decide on the level of capital in reserves (Nehme, 2011)

Market Risk

The market risk measurement remained unchanged. Every bank's Board of Director should establish committees such as "Committee Asset Liability Management and Risk" specialized in developing market risk policies based on market monitoring. There are two main models to calculate the market risk:

- The Standardized Approach which compares to the Standardized Approach in Credit Risk Calculations.
- Internal Models: that allows the banks to rely on historical statistical reports on realized and unrealized losses from previous operations on the money market (Nehme, 2011).

Counterparty Risk

One type of risk was defined in Basel III which is the counterparty risk. This type of risk includes the default risk, CVA risk charge and Asset Value Correlation. The default risk is when the creditworthiness of the borrower decreases and faces difficulties in the loan payment. The

CVA risk charge is a premium that the banks should pay to cover the mark-to-market losses . the Asset Value Correlation Multiplier requires the determination of a multiplier to the probability of default and loss given default.

Other Types of risk

BCBS has also introduced other different types of risk that were not included in the calculation of the formula. Those risks are defined as follows:

- Liquidity risk is the incapacity of the bank to meet its depositors claim on deposits at maturity without having severe losses. Liquidity risk usually arises during financial instability that is why banks should undergo stress tests during financial stability.
- Interest Rate Risk is the current or future potential risk that might affect the bank income. This is due to changes in the market interest rates levels.
- Concentration Risk is the current or future potential risk that arises when the income or the deposit for a certain bank depends on one industry, geographic location, or limited number of depositors, creditors and debtors.
- Reputational Risk is the current or future potential risk that arises from a decrease in the stakeholders of a certain bank. Lawsuits against the bank are one example that might induce reputational risk.
- Strategic Risk is the risk arising from the failure of managerial strategic decisions, actions or implementations. Inability of the bank to coop with new operational, economic and logistical changes.

- Business Risk is the risk due to inadequate products services and products offered by the bank due to wrong targeting strategies or due to unqualified employees.
- Compliance Risk arises when the bank does not abide by the rules and regulations of the regulatory committee.

Capital Adequacy Ratio Formula Changes

Basel I:

$$\text{Tier 1} + \text{Tier 2} \geq 8$$

Credit Risk Weighted Assets

Basel I Accord:

$$\text{Tier 1 Capital} + \text{Tier 2 Capital} + \text{Tier 3 Capital} \geq 8\%$$

$$[12.5 * (\text{Market Risk}) + (\text{On-balance sheet RWA} + \text{Off-balance sheet RWA})]$$

Basel II:

$$\text{Tier 1 Capital} + \text{Tier 2 Capital} + \text{Tier 3 Capital} \geq 8\%$$

$$[12.5 * (\text{Market Risk} + \text{Operational Risk}) + (\text{On-balance sheet RWA} + \text{Off-balance sheet RWA})]$$

Basel III

$$\text{Tier 1 Capital} + \text{Tier 2 Capital} \geq 10.5\%$$

$$[12.5 * (\text{Market Risk} + \text{Operational Risk}) + (\text{On-balance sheet RWA} + \text{Off-balance sheet$$

Profitability of Banks

CAMEL Model

The previous section showed the importance of the banking sector and the efforts done by the BCBS in order for it to make it a resilient sector. According to the conventional wisdom in finance, profitability is a sustainable key in the existence and the continuity of a certain business. In the following section, the determinants of profitability as well as the probable effects of CAR on bank's profitability will be discussed.

Profit is the key essential element of a financial institution existence and the cheapest source of funds. It is a necessary tool for a successful banking industry especially in a period of increasing competition. Effectively, increasing profit is an aim for all banks.

In addition, a profitable banking sector is more efficient in absorbing losses during financial crises (Olweny, 2011).

CAMEL model was used across countries to determine the factors that affect bank profitability. This model was developed by the US Federal Deposit Insurance Corporation. This model stands for Capital Adequacy, Asset quality, Management Efficiency, Earnings

performance and Liquidity. BCBS recommended the usage of this model since it early identifies the problems in banks operations (Olweny, 2011).

Capital Adequacy and Profitability

The effect of CAR and profitability will be treated in details in the following section. Since the optimal CAR calculation has been a debatable issue over economists. In Fact, while regulators recommend increasing CAR in order to increase the banking sector ability to absorb losses arising from the previously mentioned risks, bankers argue that increasing the CAR would increase the bank cost and thus reduce its competitiveness (Kock, 1995).

Asset Quality and Profitability

The quality of assets that a bank holds relies on the exposure to specific types of risks, the trend of nonperforming loans and the overall profitability. Low quality of assets will induce a higher credit risk.

As mentioned in a study conducted on the Kenyan markets, according to Burime (2008), a bank is considered to be profitable when it can forecast, avoid and monitor risks in order for it to be able to cover the potential losses arisen. Low asset quality was a major reason in collapse for many banks.

For example, 37 banks collapsed in Kenya in the early 1980s. In 1986, the major reasons behind the collapse were an increasing in the ratio of the nonperforming loans as well as to the internal excessive rating. A study done by Kosmidou (2008) showed a strong negative relationship between lower quality of assets especially on nonperforming loans and banks

profitability meaning that improving the quality of the loans granted will improve banks profitability (Olweny. 2011).

Liquidity and Profitability

According to (Kamau, 2009), Even though that by holding a high liquidity ratio, banks will be paying the opportunity cost by not investing a certain quantity of money that would generate a high return, a more liquid bank is less profitable but less risky. That's why the optimal Liquidity Ratio traps the management of a certain bank in a dilemma of liquidity and profitability

- Operational cost efficiency and Profitability

As reported by the above-mentioned study, Sufian and Chong (2008) argue that operational expense is one tool to assess bank performance. Mathuva (2009) concluded that banks with high Cost of Income Ratio (CIR) have low profitability and competitiveness compared to banks with low CIR. Overheads are one of the major components of high interest rate spreads. Overhead in unprofitable bank are driven by high staff wage costs compared to other profitable banks.

Even though, the relation between expenses and profitability is negatively correlated, in some cases the opposite is true. For example, in an uncompetitive market where banks have high power of control in the market, the cost is passed to customers making the relation between cost and profitability positive. However, this will lead to a higher interest rates and/or a lower interest on deposits (Olweny, 2011).

Diversification of Income and Profitability

The off-balance sheet was one major source of profitability in the banks. Albertazzi and Gambacorta (2006) noted that the exploration of nontraditional financial innovation and trading activities was a result of the decline in the interest margin provided by traditional operations.

The theory of portfolio diversification explains that a firm limits its risk by diversifying the source of revenues. However, the diversification of income has been a debatable issue. In fact, opponents such as Choi and Kotrozo (2006) argued that diversification provide the bank with less volatile income and increases both the economies of scope and scale. It also allows management to leverage efficiency across products (Olweny, 2011).

Opponents mentioned that income source diversification will increase the bank's complexity and might increase the potential risky behavior of managers. They also argued that the economies of scale and scope will only exist to a certain point (Olweny, 2011).

In addition to the previously mentioned internal or microeconomic components of profitability, there are other external factors related to the macroeconomic environment among those factors, expected inflation, cyclical output and overall economic performance. Other factors include the rules and regulations of a certain country that regulate arbitrage and market concentration. A high market concentration ratio lowers the profit and returns (Valentia, 2009).

Internal Factors Affecting Profitability

The internal factors also include financial which are items related directly to balance sheet and income statements and non-financial variables that include external factors not related

to financial statements. In addition to the previously mentioned factors, below are additional profitability determinants variables:

- Income: there are two major type of income generating on bank assets. Those include income and non-income profit. Profit resulting from interest on loans, overdraft, trade finance is considered to be interest income while, commissions and brokerage fees are considered to be non-interest income. Banks rely more on interest income. There is also a third type of revenue source of a bank which is generated from dividend and gains from investing in the security market (Bentum, 2012)
- Loan Quality: loans are the primary and the optimal source of earnings of a certain bank. However; banks shall be aware that when increasing their loans portfolio, they will be exposed to a higher liquidity and default risk. This might have negative repercussion of the profitability of a certain bank. For example, according to Gaurav & Kelly (2011), the increase of non-qualitative loan on residential loan has led to an increase in the Non-Performing Loans. The result was the financial crisis of the 2008. One important thing that could be affected by the non-qualitative loans is the provision took on non-performing loans which will also decrease bank's profitability (Bentum, 2012).
- Deposit: deposits are cheapest source of fund. In case of high demand for loans, the higher is the ability of a bank to raise funds, the more the bank can make loans and thus earns profits. On the other hand, if the demand for bank loans is not high, high deposit may decrease bank profitability. This due to the fact that accounts such as fixed, time and term deposits earns high interest. According to Husni (2011), ROA and Total Liability to total Assets are strongly positively related (Bentum, 2012).

- Expenses: expenses are also classified between interest and non-interest expenses. One important interest expense is the expense paid on accounts to depositors. Other non-interest expenses include operating, salaries and other miscellaneous expenses. The higher the expenses, the less profitable the bank is. Tax expense is viewed by some such as Rasiah (2010) as a separate variable that affects profitability and that is because of the significant impact on bank's profitability. According to Vong et al (2009), the existence of a positive relation between tax and profitability implies that the bank is able to offset those costs by passing the fees to customers and by increasing interest spread (Bentum, 2012).

External Factors Affecting Profitability

Macroeconomic components are external variables but that cannot be controlled by the bank. They include: GDP, interest and inflation rates, competition, market share Vs bank size and market growth (Bentum, 2012), where:

- GDP: according to Vong (2009), there is a positive relation between bank profitability and real economic growth. An increase in the real GDP growth will lead to increase demand on loans and a decrease in the rate of defaulted loans.
- Interest rate: is one major component of bank's profitability. Net interest income is the difference between interest income and interest expense. This difference is due to revenues and cost of funding. Interest rate is determined by external factors such as currency supply and demand of a certain currency in addition to market stability.

- Inflation rate: central banks have the capacity to decrease inflation. This will lead to increase in the cost of borrowing and reduce the ability of banks to give loans. This will lead to a decrease in the bank profitability.
- Competition, market share Vs Bank size and market growth, The highest the degree of competition will be the motive for banks to increase their profitability. This is explained by Michael E. Porter theory the “Rivalry among Existing Competitors. The higher is the size of the bank, the higher is the profitability of a bank. Another thing, is that if the banking sector market is growing, both new entrants and existing banks will have more incentive to keep their banks profitable.

Measurement of Bank Profitability

Ratios are the most important dependent variable in profitability analysis that is reported in the financial statements of the banks. As mentioned by Bentun (2012), in his study “The Determinants of Profitability of the Commercial Banks in Ghana during Years of Global Financial Crisis”, Rasiyah (2010) claims that ROA and ROE which the major profit ratios, are not influenced by changes in price level. One way of having an accurate profitability measure is use time series analysis. ROA is calculated by dividing the Net Income divided by Total Assets. ROAA also measure the efficiency and effectiveness of the managerial decisions of how banks transform assets to earnings. The higher the ROAA, the higher is the profitability and the efficiency of the bank. It is also a useful tool for profitability comparison between a bank and another (Bentun, 2012).

On the other hand, ROE is used to measure the return on bank's shareholders equity. In other words, it gives an idea of the earnings of shareholders on their investment. It is the ratio between the Net income after tax and shareholder's equity. As mentioned in the same study, according to Hassan and Bashir (2003), ROA is a more accurate measurement ratio than ROE since banks can use a high financial leverage to increase the ROE ratio (Bentum, 2012).

Financial Crisis

Classification of Financial Crisis

In previous sections, the interrelation between macroeconomic environment and the banking industry seems to be obvious. A healthy macroeconomic situation increases the profitability of banks and vice versa. To note that not all financial crisis took place at the level of financial institutions.

However, Banks play a major role in initiating, amplification and propagation of financial crisis. That is why regulators were always keen to issuance new rules and regulations or amend existing ones (BCBS, 2010) that would limit their repercussions on the macroeconomic level (Andries, 2009).

According to the financial Times:

A global financial crisis refers to a situation when, for reasons that may not necessarily grounded in accurate information or apparent logic, parties to financial contracts in many nations simultaneously conclude that the contracts they hold are unlikely be honored by counterparties or

that the financial assets that they hold are likely to be worth substantially less than previously thought.

The literature of the financial field segregates the financial crisis into three major three generations of crisis:

- Generation I: The first generation is specific to the 80s. Financial crisis were limited to countries with small economies with non-floating exchange rate and took the form of balance of payment where deficit took place because of internal loans.
- Generation II: Financial crisis aroused because of the speculative attacks on the European Monetary System in the 1992 and 1993 as well as the Mexican crisis the following two years. Those crises took place in a healthy stable economic environment. The main reason behind the crises was the government who had the power to defend or change the exchange rate system depending on two speculators who didn't get enough information to use the government resources.
- Generation III: Includes the recent financial crises. The reasons behind those crises were an increase in the moral hazard on the crediting process, the mutual impact of the currency on bank's behavior and the repercussions of the depreciation of the currency on the balance sheet.

According to Daianu and Lungu (2008), the crisis in the third generation can be shaped in four forms:

- Differences of maturities between short term liabilities and long terms debts that make the company unable to pay its debts and to meet depositors withdraw request

- Capital loss in currency sudden exchange rates
- Structural capital related problems related to the structure of capital when a high debt level exposes the institution to shocks resulted by the adverse reaction of the markets
- The solvency problem occurs when the bank is incapable of paying its debt through its existing assets.

As noted, both capital quantity and quality are not a cause for none of the above-mentioned crisis. However, crises of the 3rd generation have a probability of occurrence in the same of capital or liquidity problems. Causes of the crisis should be treated instead of forms of manifestation. This would be a more efficient way in preventing from future financial crises (Andries, 2009).

The 2008 Financial Crisis

According to Mark Jickling (2009), a specialist in financial economics, the financial crisis of the 2008 had many reasons. What is notable is that the financial crisis did not have any liquidity problems instead the below mentioned causes:

- High lending policies especially in the housing loan where people were able to buy unaffordable houses. This excess of lending has led to a housing bubble. The Fed was not able to recognize the bubble effects. However, even if he did policies to minimize it would have higher repercussions than waiting for the bubble to burst. Securitization was

the main reason of this bubble. It reduced bank's incentive to be careful about lending especially that the subprime loans were backed up by AAA bonds.

- Global imbalances where for example some countries such as China, Japan and Germany run large cash flow surpluses, others have encountered deficit in both domestic and government sectors.
- Lack of transparency and accountability in mortgage finance especially in contractual agreements that gave recourse to sellers of bad mortgages. Many loan takers failed to pay that caused lots of damages especially to non-bank institutions. That was due because of the absence of accountability and the wrong perception of risk managing. To get the situation worst, the rating agencies downgraded the subprime mortgage-backed securities from AAA to junk. The failure of the accurate rating was mainly due to poor economic models, conflict of interest and lack of regulations. This has led to question the reliability of the rating agencies in providing accuracy for risk calculations in the CAR formula
- Shadow banking system that allowed banks to get involved in leverage activities that increased risk. In addition to deregulatory laws such as Gramm-Leach-Bliley Act and Commodity Futures Modernization Act, that had excessive faith in market discipline, allowed banks to get involved in risky transaction. Off balance sheet finance were another reason for increasing risk. In fact, banks got engaged in risk speculative investments that created contingent liabilities. Those liabilities have made the market confidence in the bank's creditworthiness to decrease especially that investors lost the ability to understand the true financial position of a bank. As a result, many non-bank runs occurred.

- The complexity of financial innovation and the failure of risk management system, bounded rationality, relaxed excessive leverage regulations, credit default swaps, over-the-counter derivatives and tailed risk all contributed to the occurrence, propagation and the intensifying of the financial crisis.

In his book, Dr. Tim Gongdon proofed that the financial crisis of 2008 was not preceded by Lehman Brother's collapse. In fact, it began in the Great Britain in the 2007. In August 2007, the BNP Paribas announced that it will suspend withdrawal of its funds that were invested in the U. S subprime credit market.

Those funds were the components on which Northern Rock, a U.K profitable and solvent bank, relied on to maintain its liquidity. The bank was unable to insure those short-term claims. After BBC has announced this story on Monday the 13th of the 2007, a bank run occurred early the next day.

The run has led the Prime Minister Gordon Brown to guarantee all the deposits at Northern Rock. However; the announcement of Gordon, came late. The bank's stocks crashed down, investors took over the bank's assets and the bank went from liquid to an illiquid entity. As a result, the bank was nationalized and the British Financial services Authority's announced that U.K banks should increase their capital adequacy ratio.

There were two ways to increase the CAR. It is either by increasing the money or by decreasing the riskiness of the bank's assets. In both cases, the money won't be in balance and the balance sheets will shrink. As a result, the money supply in the U. K is at a deficit of 13% even though the bank of England has used a quantitative easing program in March of the 2009

and that led to a money supply of 22.3%. The same is true for the US markets where the money supply registers a deficit of 6.73%.

Factors Affecting Capital Adequacy Ratio Performance

William (1998) as appears in a study on the factors that affect the performance of CAR argues that the CAR calculation should be based mainly on macroeconomic determinants such as inflation, money supply and political instability (Mili, 2014)

On the other side, the BSBC aim is to provide a uniformed CAR to be adopted by all countries (BCBS, 2010).

As noted previously,

- The CAR quality is not the real reason behind any financial crisis instead it is one possible way of a crisis manifestation.
- The CAR and as per Basel recommendation can be calculated using different models in risk, operational and market risk meaning that the same CAR in two different countries will not be reflecting the same capacity of loss absorbing.
- CAR and profitability relationship is affected by many factors that will be developed in the next coming section:

Capital Adequacy Ratio and Pro cyclical Problem

The International Monetary fund, the Financial Stability Board and the BCBS introduced new rules and regulations to reduce pro cyclical effects and increase countercyclical ones

(Repullo, 2011). However; below mentioned studies show that the adoption of a high capital adequacy ratio might introduce pro cyclical effects on the overall economy (Covas, 2010)

According to Landau, Pro cyclical refers to the capacity of financial variables to have an effect on economic fluctuation (Landau, 2009)

The relation between capital adequacy and profitability depends on their actual CAR and how it relates to their optimal CAR. Economic cycle is one important factor that affects this relationship (Osborne, 2009)

The credit crunch during the early 90s, the Asian and Spanish crises and the bankruptcies in the 2000s approved the theoretical approach of the pro cyclical of the financial sector and the economy. Hancock and Wilcox 1994 and Wagster 1991 argued that imposing tougher risk-based capital standards, increasing supervisory toughness and moving to a higher classification of assets led to an increase in the pro cyclical effect of the financial system (Berger, 2004).

One effect of the pro cyclical CAR is on the monetary policy. A bank facing a constraint to increase its CAR will prevent the bank to increase its loans even if the demand for loans increases in the market leading expansionary monetary policies to be ineffective.

Another thing is that during an economic downturn, the quantity of the risk held by underlying assets will increase since risk is highly correlated with the business cycle leading to a decrease in the overall CAR. As a reaction, banks should either increase their capital or decrease their risk weighted average or to increase their capital. In a recession, it is difficult for a bank to

raise its capital. A decrease in the lending will be the adequate solution leading to a decrease in the bank profitability and to worsening the downturn in the economy (Nye, 2010).

A Study conducted by both Lin and Hu, showed that the requirement on the capital should be lowered during a recession period and strengthened during boom period. The ratio of the capital adequacy should be determined depending on two important factors, the degree of moral hazard and the return on investment of a certain loan in a certain economic situation. The reasons behind this conclusion is that when a bank imposes higher CAR, the depositors and insiders will shift from depositing to equity investment leading to a decrease in the provision on deposits. As a result, the loans availability fund will increase. At this time the bankrupt protection will reduce and that is due to the shrinkage on deposit (lin et al, nd)

When the economic situation gets better, interest on both loans and banks will increase as a result, the cost of raising the capital will decrease and that is due to higher profits (Lin) in addition to a decrease in the underlying risk of a bank asset (Nye, 2010)

Excess capital growth can lead to a financial crisis. In fact, banks continue to increase their market share by increasing loans, pay excessive dividends a buy back their shares and that is to give the impression of a resilient banking sector. However, capital buffer should be built up during periods of excess profit and that is due to a decreased cost of capital raising and an increase of moral hazard problem (BCBS, 2011).

The studies conducted on the Japanese financial sector during its economical crisis that started in the first quarter of the 1991 till the last quarter of 2008 showed that the CAR should have been lowered by a 2.1%, However; studies on the US market showed that the CAR should

have been lowered by 4.42% during the boom period that started from the fourth quarter of the 2002 till the fourth quarter of the 2007 (Yoshino, 2009).

Capital Requirement and Risk Problem

One of the main objectives of the regulations is to make the banks shift from the usage of risky assets to non-risky ones, however; theories have argued this fact. For example, Kahane 1977 as well as Koehn and Santomero 1980 concluded that the risk-based capital adequacy ratio will not make banks to avoid the usage of risky assets; in contrast, it will lead them to do so.

- Higher capital requirement will increase outside equity leading to an increase in the moral hazard. Moral hazard when employees of a certain bank may engage in risk sharing activities in condition that this activity affects outcome distribution probability. In this case the moral hazard is manifested through the cost of increasing the CAR. In fact, a study conducted on US banks showed that there was a decrease of a USD 28 in their share price for every dollar raised by new equity (Baer, 1992).
- The main source of moral hazard is asymmetric information (Hölmstrom, 1979).
Another thing is that upon an increase in the capital requirements, the loan size equilibrium will increase as well as the equilibrium interest rate but a decrease in the deposit rate equilibrium. A higher CAR has a same effect as the tax effect meaning that a bank shifting to less risky assets will decrease its competition for deposits. Due to competition, depositors might shift to other competitive banks. A decrease in the rate of deposit will also increase bank's risk (Santomero, 1980).

Santomero and Kohen developed a model to test the riskiness of a certain bank before and after an increase in the CAR where they found that the underlying risk of institutions' portfolio before adoption of the CAR is equivalent to the risk associated to the new CAR. They also concluded that the degree of riskiness of a certain bank as well as bankruptcy prediction cannot be appropriately predicted by the CAR (Santomero, 1980).

Capital Adequacy Ratio and Profitability

The relation between CAR and profitability has been a debatable issue and that is because of the degree of influence pro cyclical, moral hazard, cost of income and the risk effect varies from a bank to the other. Below, mentioned theories that relate to the efficiency of the CAR in a certain bank that take into consideration the previously mentioned factors.

- The pecking order theory argues that a CAR depends on the ability of a bank to internally generate fund from past profitable transactions. Internal funds will lower its cost of increasing capital and to grasp new investment opportunities. Profitable banks can have the opportunity to lower their optimal CAR (Osborne,2009)
- The trade-off theory argues that raising capital in financial distress reduces risk of the bank and hence, the lowers its cost of bankruptcy. A bank that has his CAR below its optimal one will have a positive relation with profitability if the bank tends to increase its capital and vice versa. It also argues that high capital requirements are costly for banks so the relation between capital adequacy and profitability depends to the extent the current CAR stands from the optimal CAR. The tradeoff theory implies that imposed

requirements should tradeoff between cost and benefits of capitals leading to a zero relation at the margin (Osborne,2009).

- The study of Berger, 1995 concluded that the level of a bank optimal CAR is cyclical and the relation between optimal CAR and profitability tends to be positive during financial distress. He also argued that the optimal CAR should increase by itself in times of financial distress and that is due to management decision to give assurance to depositors (Osborne,2009).

Berger conducted a study on the US banks during the period of 1980s and the 1990s. During the first period, the financial sector in the USA has witnessed the saving and loan crisis, many banks went bankrupted as a result a recession occurred. At the same time banks were undercapitalized because of financial distress (Osborne, 2009).

In the period of the 1990s, the economic recession was controlled and the CAR started to rise in the US banks. However, Berger found a positive relation between CAR and profitability during the first period, whereas; a negative relation was found during the second period. The results of Berger contrast the recent data of the US banks that revealed that the CAR should have been lowered in the 2008 crisis and that is in order for regulators to prohibit the CAR to offset the expansionary monetary policy. According to the trade off theory, the possible explanation to this observation is that in the first period, banks that were able to increase their CAR to get to their optimal CAR manifested a positive relation (Osborne,2009).

A high CAR in a stressed market leads the bank to earn more profits and that due to lower interest rates paid on uninsured debt. While in the second period, the surplus of CAR, due

to highly retained earnings from previous profitable transactions in addition of market discipline, exceeded its optimal level explaining the negative relationship (Osborne,2009).

Those results are in line with the tradeoff theory, since the cost of increasing Capital did not trade off the benefits of this increase. Another thing is that an optimal CAR will limit the procyclicality effects this is shown in the Japanese market where the CAR should have been lowered to reach its optimal and boost the expansionary monetary policy adopted by the government. While American market where CAR had to be lowered in the period of excessive growth in order for it to limit the excess profitability that might lead to a financial crisis (Osborne,2009).

To conclude, CAR depends on cycles, a bank can increase its profitability by adjusting to its optimal CAR. There is a close to zero relationship between an optimal capital adequacy ratio and profitability. Short-term optimal CAR will automatically auto correct themselves in response for long term deviation (Osborne.2009).

This study will be focused on the Lebanese banking sector where it will project the previously mentioned theories along with empirical studies observations. In the following section, a general overview on the adoption of Basel implementation as well as a brief of the current financial situation will be developed.

Lebanese Financial Market and BCBS Implementation

Lebanese Financial Sector Features

According to the Association of Bankers of Lebanon, the Lebanese banking sector is stable and resilient one. It plays a major role in the overall performance of the macroeconomic level of the country. In fact, according to the Investment Development Authority of Lebanon (IDAL), the total assets of operating banks increased from USD 136.9 Billion in 2011 to 145.9 Billion at the end of the 2012. This increase has an average of 6% that is equivalent of 345% of GDP. Another thing is the deposit rate that increased by 5.9% at the end of the 2012 counting a 264.4% of the GDP. The Lebanese sector is characterized by its liquidity where liquidity ratio stands at 82% (IDAL, 2013).

Lebanese banks fall ruled and monitored by the Bank of Lebanon. Entry to banking industry, definition of the scope of banking activities and setting rules of practice for banks are among the major roles of BDL (ABL, 2011)

The progress and resilience of the banking sector are results of the BDL strict rules and regulation and the supervision of the Banking Control Commission (BCC). The BCC has the authority of supervision over the banks and of ensuring compliance with bank behavior and BDL's regulations (ABL, 2011)

In an interview with the daily stars, Ghobril, Head of Economic Research at Byblos bank, announced that in the 2009, while the world was facing a serious economic crisis, the Lebanese sector enjoyed a high growth rate and that was due to a relative local political stability.

In the 2011, the resilient Lebanese banking sector was put under pressure and that is due to three main causes: the global financial slowdown, the internal unstable political situation in addition to the Syrian war.

He also added that the pressure on the Lebanese banking sector as well as will continue at the same slow growth of the 2011. Even though, there was an increase of deposits and profits in the 2011 but the rate of growth was lower than previous years (Sakr, 2011).

In an interview with the Executive (Sioufi, 2013), BDL governor, Riad Salemech clarified the following:

Between 2015 and 2019, we might demand higher tier one capital. It is not the end of the exercise. We want banks to strengthen their capital and have quality capital. We are also pushing so the credit will not be affected. We don't have to see them improve the ratio by decreasing their credit.

On the other hand, studies conducted by Lebanese researchers showed that Lebanese CAR, Cost of Income, Return on Assets and equities are not highly performing ratios.

Dr. Barakat, a researcher at Audi Bank who conducted a study on the Lebanese market marked the following evidence:

- The average ROA in the Lebanese commercial bank sector stands at 1.1% the lowest when compared to MENA, emerging and the world ROA. The average ROE stands on 12.3% same as the average banking industry in the world, highest that MENA region - that stands at 12% and lowest that the emerging countries that stand at rate of 13.2%

- The Cost of Income stands at 50.1% highest from both the MENA and the emerging markets and lowest from the world average
- The CAR of the four categories of banks stand respectively for Alfa, Beta Gamma and Delta banks stand respectively at 12.5, 12.4, 18.2 and 37.8 per cent respectively. On the other hand, the Return on Average Equity (ROAE) is respectively, 13.0%, 9.5%, 7.3% and 5.8%.

Those figures add to the previously mentioned reasons behind bank profitability, that the profitability of a certain bank is related to both its size and its efficiency. A study on the Lebanese market will be developed in details in the previous section.

The annual consolidated financial statements of the three banks show that there has been a constant increase in the loan credit amount. On the other hand, the profitability ratio did not increase accordingly. This phenomenon might have several reasons behind it such as inefficiency due to high COI or a constant increasing in the CAR. For example, BLOM Bank net loans in the Lebanese market have increased from US 1,670M in the 2005 till US 6,345M in the 2013 while for example ROAA have increased for the same period from 1.2% till 1.38% while the ROCE had decreased from 17.21% till 16.7%.

In the 25th of March 1998, Banque du Liban (BDL), issued a circular obliging Lebanese bank to adopt the CAR calculation of Basel I with a minimum ratio of 10% instead of 8% as set by Basel I accord. In the 1st of April 2006, BDL issued a new circular in which he insisted that all banks should adopt the Basel II recommendation starting from December 1st of the 2008. It also specified the approaches that should be adopted in the calculation of the different types of risks.

- Standardized approach for both market and credit risk
- Basic Indicator Approach for operational risk

Advanced approaches were allowed to be used after the approval of the banking supervision committee (Nehme, 2011).

The Basel III recommendations were to be implemented in Lebanon starting from the issuance of the Circular N 358 on the 6th of March 2014. All Lebanese banks should fully meet the changes recommended in the quality of capital held in tier 1 and tier 2 by the end of the 2015 (BDL circular, 358). The minimum CAR set by BDL stands at 12%. Today's Lebanese average CAR of all banks according to Basel II stands at 12.2% (Barakat, 2014).

Banking Efficiency

Banking Efficiency Definition

According to the business dictionary, efficiency is the comparison of what is actually produced or performed with what can be achieved with what can be achieved with the same consumption of resources such as money, time and labor. It is an important factor in determination of productivity.

The COI is a ratio that measures efficiency of a certain bank. Per definition, is the ratio of non-interest costs, excluding bad and doubtful debt expense, divided by the total of the net interest income and non-interest income. The cost of income reflects the controllable costs that can be decreased by managerial decisions and implementations without a change in the overall output level (Tripe, 1998).

Relationship between Cost of Income and Profitability

A study done on 11 European countries have shown that there is a positive relationship between the size of capitalization and the cost efficiency. Another thing is that foreign banks are to be considered more efficient because they take a less risky strategy

- There was a positive relation between the size of a bank and its cost of income efficiency. That is due to the ability of banks to attain a lower cost per unit meaning a high probability of increasing return.
- The Equity to Asset ratio was also found to be positively correlated with efficiency. This is due to a decrease in the moral hazard problem between management and owners. Owners will get a higher motivation to implement cost efficiency policies inside the bank so that the cost will decrease
- The relation between the loans to asset ratio was significantly negative. The highest was the loan to asset ratio, the less cost efficient was the bank. This could be due to poor credit assessment
- There is a positive but not with strong significance relation between cost of income efficiency and ROAE (Pancurova, 2013).

The first measurement of the efficiency of a certain bank focused on the financial ratio as well as both, the economies of scale and scope. However; as mentioned by Molyneux, Altunbas and Gardener (1996) on a study on the European banks, they noted other measurement type of efficiency which are allocative and technical efficiencies making the two components of X-efficiency. X-efficiency reveals the managerial ability and differences to control cost or maximize profit.

It is commonly known that an increase in the competition would induce managers to cut costs in order for them to remain profitably competitor. On the other hand, empirical results did not imply a positive or a negative relationship between efficiency and profitability.

Competition is one determinant of this relation. While Casu and Girardrone (2006) found a negative relation between efficiency and market competition

Dr. Little conducted a survey of 51 major European banks. He found out that the most efficient banks have a COI lower than 40%. The same study concluded that the COI is increasing over time. The most efficient banks were found to have the right cost cut culture, high degree of investment in IT, flat hierarchies and decentralized decision-making centers and the usage of key performance check list (Little, 2008). Targets that help banks to increase their efficiencies are listed below:

- Profitability targets: when a bank sets for itself a target of increasing profitability, it is indirectly setting targets for cost cutting. As explained before, competition is one major factor to determine bank's efficiency. Managers would cut cost in order for them to increase their market share, thus; their profit.

- Cost-income ratio targets: when a bank cuts all the cost not directly related to production. The management will have an incentive to focus on as much as profits it can get from the investment. Cost reduction programs can also be developed. Management can compare the performance of the bank in lined with the set targets.

- Cost growth targets: it is when the cost is explicitly announced to all employees whom are also responsible for cost cutting.

According to the same previously mentioned study conducted by Dr. Barakat, there is an increasing external burden in the operating environment of the Lebanese banks. As a result, Lebanese banks have implemented measures to cut cost and to increase profitability.

However; he found that there is little internal optimization incentive to increase cost efficiency. That was shown by a high operating expense to average assets that stood at 1.52% as well a cost of income averaging 50.1% in the 2012. The cost of income in the Lebanese market is negatively related to the size of the bank. The higher the size of a certain bank, the lower is its COI and that is because of the economies of scale. The same study continues to conclude that profits are not related to the CAR. Alfa banks that are holding the lowest CAR are holding the highest ROAE that stands on 13% while Gamma Banks reported a ROAE of 7.3% (Barakat, 2013).

CHAPTER 3

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

My research requires gathering relevant data from the specified documents and compiling databases in order to analyze the material and get to a more complete understanding and historical reconstruction. In order to fulfill the destined outcome, the survey will be conducted using both quantitative and qualitative approach. The quantitative approach will prove the hypothesis correctly of whether there is a relation between the level of CAR, COI and profitability or not, whereas the qualitative approach will back up our results through face to face interviews with professional qualified entities.

Through the research: We will shed lights on the following questions:

Taking Basel probable proposal that an increase in the CAR will increase the resiliency of the banking sector and the probable previously mentioned repercussions,

- a. Would be able to prevent from another financial crisis?
- b. Would be able to increase the profitability of banks?
- c. Does one CAR perform the same in different situations?
- d. Is CAR an adequate tool to measure bank solvency?

- e. Does a decrease in the Lebanese CAR reduce the trust given by investors and local depositors to the Lebanese financial sector?

The purpose of the study is to show that a high CAR will not increase the profitability in the Lebanese banking sector. Instead, it might decrease it in some cases that will be explained in the next coming chapter. The COI would have a high impact on the Lebanese banking industry. A decrease in both, CAR and COI, will at that time lead to a significant increase in the profitability ratios in the banking industry. That what explains the necessity of using Pearson correlation which measures the change of one variable relative to the other.

Instruments

The survey will be conducted using face-to-face interviews with a sample of N= 9 respondents selected from the top alpha banks; sought from level of experience, high managerial key positions related to straight banking financial dealings as to investigate positive and negative insight they have occurred during the application of the rules and procedures of Basel. In addition, the key informant approach will be used for data collection.

A. Confidentiality

All methods and procedures described in this survey comply with the rules and regulations of the ICC/ESOMAR code for International Marketing and Social Research Practice, and the regulations of the Central Statistical Office CSO on social research practice.

Research Questions and CAR Performance

As previously mentioned, there has been a debate concerning the concept of CAR. While the BCBS recommends the adoption of a uniformed CAR and that is to address the lessons learned from previous financial crisis, some argue that implementing the recommendations of Basel will make the banking sector to bear additional repercussions such as offsetting expansionary monetary policy, decreasing profitability and inducing more risk to the bank.

According to a cross-country study conducted by the International Monetary fund, a CAR does not perform in the same way in different circumstances and that is due to the following arguments (Le Lesle, 2012):

- The capital measurement allowed to be used and that are mentioned in the 3rd pillar allows the calculations of the CAR based on individual techniques that allow banks to tamper their capital base. This means that a high capital adequacy does not necessarily reflects a well-capitalized bank.
- Same CAR may hide different underlying risks and that is because of the different measurement used methods. In fact, in 2011 some banks have decreased their Risk Weighted Assets; however there was not a noted improvement in the overall strength of a bank as well as in its risk management policies.
- Difference in regulatory environment, accounting approaches such IFRS or GAAP, banks' business strategies, quality and composition of RWAs as well as methodologies used.

- Degree of Pro Cyclical effects on each country that will be reflected by the economic stage, financial stability, rates of defaults by regions, countries and asset class in addition to rate of recovery.
- The run phenomena or the liquidity phenomena are a result of a financial crisis not the reasons behind them. For example, the run in the great depression was because of the crash on the market stock. People lost confidence in their financial systems and a run occurred. In the 2008 financial crisis, the previously discussed reasons behind the occurrence of the crisis, did not mention any run reason. However; bankers developed imprudent lending strategies, bad risk management behaviors and high leverage activities reasons.
- Changing reasons behind every financial crisis. In fact, not all the rules and regulation were able to prevent from the occurrence of another financial crisis. For example, the S&L, the Rumasa and the Continental Illinois had respectively the following reasons: dramatic changes in interest rates, licenses for inexperienced entrepreneurs and industry concentration investments.
- The degree of moral hazard in each bank and the management response to it.

The study of Dr. Marwan conducted on the Lebanese banking sector in the same year and on the different bank sectors in Lebanon shows that the bigger is the size of a certain bank, the more efficient is the CAR. Even though the CAR of Delta group banks is three times more than Alfa banks, the ROAE of Alfa banks is 2.3 times higher than Delta group banks. To note, the COI is inversely related to the size of the bank because of the low cost per transaction. That is also in line with the theory of the economies of scales.

Taking into consideration the following facts:

- The US data and the Japanese data that showed that the CAR should be respectively lowered in the Boom period of the American economy that preceded the financial crisis of 2008 and decreased during the economic recession of Japan.
- The Study done on the US banks during the 80s showed that during a financial distress there was a positive relation between the CAR and the profitability ratios. In Fact; the optimal CAR by itself tends to increase in financial distress. The extended study of Berger proves that there is a zero relation between a bank CAR and profitability when the bank CAR is set at its optimal. If the CAR is set above its optimal, an increase in the CAR will lead to a decrease in the income. If CAR is set below its optimal, an increase in the CAR will lead to an increase in the profitability ratios.
- The theories that treat the relation between CAR and profitability ratios: the pecking order theory that argues that a bank should generate its capital from past profitable transactions. The trade off theory that proves that the performance of CAR on the profitability is related to the level of the current ratio relative to the optimal CAR.
- The fact that CAR is a manifestation or a result of a certain financial problem and shall be treated by treating the main cause of the financial problem.
- The study of Santomero and Koehn that concluded that a high CAR will not decrease banks riskiness. Instead, they might induce banks to choose more risky assets. In addition, they cannot be an effective tool to predict a bankruptcy.
- The fact that not all the defined risk is used to calculate the CAR.
- The failure of previously set rules and regulations to offset from other financial crisis and that is because, as explained before, of changes in the reasons, type and repercussions of financial crises.

- The fact that the economist estimated that Lehman Brother's CAR was 11% five days prior of its declaration of its bankruptcy.

Based on the above-mentioned facts adopting the Basel CAR is not the optimal choice for lots of country especially the ones that are going under recession. If the CAR is not set as its optimal, it will not be able to prevent from a financial crisis and that is due to the fact that CAR is cyclical. The optimal CAR differs from a bank to the other and that is due to many factors such as the size of the bank and the degree of pro cyclicity a certain CAR generates on the GDP.

For the same bank, certain X level of a CAR might be optimal under certain circumstances might not be in others. Profitability of the bank depends on the degree the current CAR stands when compared to the optimal CAR of the bank. Thus, inadequately capitalized bank might face profitability problems. To note that profitability is an ultimate objective of profitable business and a sustainable key element in its existence. That is why the adoption of Basel recommendations will not necessarily increase bank's profitability and thus will not necessarily prevent from another financial crisis. In addition, this is also true because of the changes in reasons behind financial crisis and liquidity issues are a result not a reason.

Data Collection and Analysis

The data is collected annually between 2004 and 2013 from the top three biggest banks in Lebanon Audi, BLOM and Byblos banks. The reason why these banks are used is because according to Bankdata they represent the three largest banks in Lebanon. In fact, Audi bank at March of 2012 had the highest total assets standing at US 28.7Billion, shareholder's equity at 2.5B, and customers' deposits at US. Concerning the loan and profit they stand respectively at US8.9B and profit at 94.5M.

BLOM bank has the lowest COI when compared to its peers that what helped him to boost its profitability ratios. In fact its ROCE reached the highest and stood at 17.7%. Total Assets of BLOM bank stood at 23.8B In Q1 2012.

The purpose of the research is to show the effects the implementation of the BCBS recommendation have had on the banking sector in the Lebanese market. That is why the correlation between variables was calculated from 2004 till 2006 of Basel I adoption and from 2008 till 2010 of Basel II adoption and from 2011 till of Basel III adaptation. The correlation between variables of the total 2004-2013 will be also calculated. This will have an objective to get a more precise idea about the relation between variables. They will be used to add more clarification on the relation between the variables. It will also be used for scenario analysis in case of a decrease or an increase in the CAR.

The correlation changes between the variable will give an idea of the constraints Lebanese banks have had to face to meet Basel requirements. To note, the minimal CAR by itself did not increase from 8% but the quality of the components of the tiers from Basel I till Basel II.

On the other side, changes on both qualitative and quantitative levels were introduced from Basel II till Basel III where the minimum CAR was set at 10.5%. In Lebanon the three banks are compliant with the BDL recommendation to implement Basel Accord.

As previously explained, Basel III has induced more constraints on both the qualitative and quantitative level of the CAR. This means that the repercussions on profitability and COI will be higher if those three banks decided to have an additional increase on their current level of CAR and CAR each alone and combined.

The three banks are commercial and listed on Beirut Stock Exchange, and our ambition is that the sample result will be applicable to the banking market in Lebanon as a whole. All the data collected are expressed in percent, which help to reduce the problem caused by the fact that the bank used are of different sizes. The three banks are Alpha banks meaning that the clients' deposits are above 2B It is the sector that was able to have the highest growth rate between the 2012 and the 2013 where this rate stood at 10.1%. It is the sector that showed the highest resiliency against the changing environment as well as the lowest CAR (Barakat, 2013).

The reason why annual data is used instead of quarterly or monthly, which would have provided us with a larger sample, is because we thought that many financial decisions that banks take are on yearly basis. They might take financial decisions that are not meant to be shown in the result before the end of the year due to time lags in the implementation processes. Further, it is much easier to find annual data ten years back in time compared with monthly data which is not always stated. Because of this, we thought that yearly data were the most adequate to use for the aim of our analysis.

All the data has been collected from the databases of BDL and each bank annual financial report, which both are used worldwide. We consider these sources trustworthy as they are public and available for everyone so any person who intends to collect the same numbers as we have done can do so by using the same sources. All the banks are using standardized accounting systems accepted by International Accounting Standards (IAS), and International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS), for exchange listed companies

All the numbers are also calculated at least twice to minimize the risk of errors caused by us.

Program used Description

The statistical program SPSS was used for the regression. SPSS is a broadly used program for statistical surveys, and the reliability of it has been proved by many researchers before. We have also done a correlation to see that there is a relation (inverse or direct) between the independent variables we stated.

A. Variables

As a derivation we need to explain for each bank for the year of 2003 and 2007 and from 2009 and 2013 and for the total meaning from 2003 till 2013 the correlation between:.

- CAR and COI
- CAR and ROE
- CAR and ROA

- COI and ROE
- COI and ROA

Below is the acronym definition

- CAR= Capital Adequacy Ratio
- COI= Cost Of Income
- ROCE= Return On Common Equity
- ROAA= Return On Average Assets

We will then compare for each bank the changes in the correlation whether it was an increase or a decrease. We will also compare the interrelation of those variables between banks.

Correlation Description

Correlation analysis is used to measure strength of the association (linear relationship) between two variables below are mentioned the characteristics of correlation coefficient:

- Only concerned with strength of the relationship
- No causal effect is implied
- Can also have curvilinear relationships in data
- Correlation coefficient r
- p-value
- Pearson correlation is an effect size measure

Positive Effect

$|r| = .1$ small effect

$|r| = .3$ medium effect

$|r| = .5$ large effect

Negative Effect

$|r| = -.n$ (negative variable) means there is an inverse relationship

Qualitative Data Collection

A qualitative evaluation shall be utilized for this research project leveraging subjective methods such as interviews and observations to collect substantive and relevant data. These interviews shall be conducted with practicing financial leaders from reputable institutions as well as financial experts so as to enrich our evaluation with an expert prospective point of view that will eventually back up our quantitative result analysis. The survey will be conducted through face-to-face interviews with administrative representative sample from the top 3 alpha banks in Lebanon (BLOM, BYBLOS & AUDI).

Such a qualitative approach is valuable here due to the varying experiences of the representative financial experts. Upon collecting the qualitative data derived from said interviews, careful analysis shall be done (both manually and utilizing NIPO/(ODINS) software) to prepare a SWOT (strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats) to analyze how to best customize the course to the target outcome.

Finally the same CAR does not reflect the same capitalization level in terms of dollars that is why it is not an absolute accurate tool to predict bank solvency and bankruptcy.

One important thing to be noted is that before Lehman Brother's collapse its CAR stood at 11% meaning that it was beyond the level of Basel recommendations. Still, the bank went from liquid to illiquid overnight. Another thing is the real reasons behind the financial crisis of the 2008. The bank's management behavior by itself induced risk to the banking sector and that is because banks got engaged into risky actions. This study confirms that a run or the liquidity problem is a result of a financial crisis.

An unexpected factor, leads to a panic in the market. The higher the panic caused by a certain event, the higher is the run size. Accordingly, the strategy of the management, their engagement in risky activities and their leverage exposure are a more efficient tool in predicting bank failure.

The next section will extend those findings on the Lebanese banking sector. It will show that the implementation of Basel by the Lebanese banks have had a negative effects on the profitability of the Alfa banks.

CHAPTER 4

DATA ANALYSIS

Report on the Empiric Work

This section will give a detailed description about the statistical results found between the variables such as the changes in the correlations between the four variables for each bank across four phases. The first phase is the correlation for the total period, the following are for Basel I, II and II respectively. It will also give a description of the real numbers of the three banks as well as a comparison of the variable performance between banks.

Before analyzing the results of the three banks and after discussing different points of view related to the optimal level of the CAR , it be useful to say that the concept of an optimal CAR is relative to each country especially

Graph Description

Performance by Bank

- a. Audi Bank

During the period of 2004 and 2006 what we can notice is a simultaneous increase in the CAR between the profitability ratio except for the year 2006 where the dramatic increase in the CAR was concurrent with the decrease in the ROAA but with an increase in the ROCE. Concerning the COI it had an inverse relationship with the CAR and a ROCE. The marginal changes for CAR, ROCE and ROAA are respectively an increase of 10.57%, 0.89%, 0.46% and a decrease of COI of 9.94%

In the 2008 what is notable is the intersection point between the CAR and the ROCE. From 2008 till 2010 we can notice that there is a decrease in the CAR while the ROCE has witnessed an increase. The ROAA is also increasing with a decrease in the CAR between the years 2009 and 2010 with a small decrease of 0.01% in the 2010 compared to a decrease of 1.25% of the CAR. The COI is at a decreasing path. A decrease in the COI is coincident with a decrease in the CAR an increase in the profitability ratios.

The increase in the CAR for the year 2012 has led to a decrease in the ROCE and to an increase in the ROAA while the decrease of the CAR has led to a decrease in both ROCE and ROAA in the 2013. The COI has decreased from the 2011 till the 2012 but had a dramatic increase from the 2012 till the 2013. The lines of the CAR and the ROCE will intersect eventually in coming years if the correlation between those variable remains intact (figure 1)

b. BLOM Bank

In the 2004- 2006, there is a positive relation between the CAR and the ROAA, this relation is true for CAR and ROCE during the 2004 and 2005 when it turns to be negative

between the 2005 and 2006. The COI has inverse relation with both profitability ratios for all the period and with the CAR for the period of 2004 and 2005 that turned to be positive in the 2006.

In the 2008-2009, there is a negative relation between the CAR and the profitability ratios that turns out to be positively correlated in the 2009 and 2010. The COI is positively correlated with the CAR but negatively correlated with the profitability ratios. In the 2011 the positive relation between the CAR and profitability turned out to be negative with a continuous increase in the CAR will lead to a constant decrease in both ROCE and ROAA. To note, that the ROAA and ROCE lines will eventually intersect after 2013 (figure 3)

c. Byblos Bank

During the 2004-2006 there is an inverse relation between CAR and COI meaning that an increase in the CAR will lead to a decrease in COI. There is also an inverse relation between COI and the ROCE for all the years this also true for the relation between COI and ROAA between 2004- 2005. This relation turns to be insignificantly positive between 2005 and 2006. The CAR has a positive relation with the ROAA but an insignificant positive relation with the ROAA for the 2004 and an insignificant negative relation during the 2005-2006.

In the 2008-2009, there is a positive relationship between the CAR and the COI. The same is true for the relation of the CAR and the ROAA. Concerning the CAR and the ROCE the relation is negative for all years meaning that an increase in the CAR will lead to a decrease in the profitability ratio. The CAR and the ROCE have intersected slightly before the 2008 and slightly after the 2009. Between those intersections lines remain the negative relation between the cAR and the profitability ratios.

Concerning the 2010 -2013, there is an inverse relationship between the CAR and the profitability ratios. Both ROCE and ROAA tend to decrease when the CAR increases. The COI had a positive relation with the CAR and thus a negative relation with profitability ratios (figure2)

Ratio Comparison between Banks

a. Capital Adequacy Ratio

- What is noticeable is that between 2004 till 2007 the CAR of BLOM was the highest along all years with a clear advantage over Byblos and a huge gap with Audi.
- CAR of Byblos Vs. Audi witnessed an inverse turning point as of 2005-2006 where Byblos declined drastically and Audi inclining to top the 2nd position and as of 2006-2007 they came close with a miniature advantage for Byblos.
- As for the years between 2007 till 2013 we noticed a huge inclination of CAR ration across all banks nevertheless BLOM & Byblos alter in topping where in the year (2009) BLOM was leading then Audi took the lead in (2010-2011-2012) finally in 2013 BLOM mounted again on top of both Byblos & Audi.

One anomaly was found in the year of 2008 where Audi overcome both Byblos & BLOM

- The average CAR (n) for the 3 banks, BLOM bank, Byblos bank and Audi are respectively as follows: 20.84%, 17.25% and 15.52% (Figure 4)

b. Cost of Income Ratio

- What is evident is that between 2003 till 2013 the COI for BLOM across all year was the lowest with a huge gap between Audi & Byblos.
- The trend of inclination and declination of both Audi and Byblos were fluctuating variably across all years whereas we can notice an advantage for Audi in most of the years over Byblos except for 2 years in (2006-2012) where Audi has a higher percentile.
- The average COI (n) for the 3 banks Audi bank, Byblos bank and BLOM bank are respectively as follows: 52.43%, 49.59% and 36.79% (see Figure 5).

c. Return on Average Asset

- The ROA Trend for BLOM dominated both Byblos and Audi overall years except for the one anomaly in 2012 where Audi topped with a slight advantage over BLOM.
- ROA Byblos trend vs. Audi in the 2005 they almost matched but afterwards in 2006 till 2013.
- The ROA Trend for Audi showed a higher inclination than that of Byblos with a noticeable gap
- The average ROA (n) for the 3 banks BLOM bank, Audi Bank and Byblos Bank are as follow: 1.35%, 1.18% and 1.05% (see Figure 6)

d. Return on Common Equity

- The ROCE Trend for BLOM Bank dominated topped both Byblos and Audi over all years with a huge gap over the ROCE trend of both Audi and Byblos
- The trend of inclination and declination of both Audi & Byblos were fluctuating variably across all years while we can notice an advantage for Audi in the first 3 years over Byblos (2004-2005-2006) until the year 2007 where Byblos trend had a turning point

overcoming Audi and lasting till 2009 where another turning point occurring but this time for Audi and continuing on till 2013

- The average ROCE (n) for the 3 banks BLOM bank, Audi Bank and Byblos bank are respectively as follows: 19.49%, 14.63% and 12.63% (Figure 7)

The relation between CAR and COI is shown in figures 8, 9 and 10 respectively shows that there is a positive relation between those two variables for both Audi and Byblos banks while for BLOM it is negative but negligible almost linear. This could be explained by the lowest COI in terms of dollars BLOM bank is having. Another thing is the negative relation between COI and CAR as well as between CAR and profitability ratios from the other side.

Correlation Description

What is notable upon analyzing the correlations between variables across all banks for the total years is that there is an inverse relationship between CAR and profitability ratios as well as negative relation between COI and profitability ratios. The COI and CAR changes over banks where it is positive for both Audi and Byblos banks it turns to be insignificantly negative for BLOM Bank.

A. Audi bank

The correlation between CAR and ROAA is insignificant but negative and it stands at 0.22393 in absolute value. The relation between CAR and ROCE is moderately negative and stands at 0.52063 in absolute value. The correlation between COI and Both ROAA and ROCE is

strongly negative and stand respectively at 0.69934 and 0.84465 in absolute values. Finally the relation between the COI and the CAR between is moderately positive and stands at 0.378368 (figure 11)

B. BLOM bank

The correlation between CAR and profitability ratio is strongly negative in both cases where it stands respectively for ROAA and ROCE at 0.59841 and 0.65002. What is notable is that the correlation between the COI and profitability ratio is strongly negative with ROAA but insignificant with the ROCE. It stands at 0.6734 for the ROAA and 0.24376 for the ROCE. The relation between the COI and the CAR is negative but insignificant and it stands at 0.0518 in absolute value (see Figure 9).

C. Byblos Bank

The correlation between the CAR and profitability ratios is strongly negative for both profitability ratios. It stands at 0.668869 for ROA and at 0.52331 for ROCE. The correlation between COI and profitability ratio is also negative. It is strongly positive for ROA where it stands at 0.68869 and moderate for ROCE where it stands at 0.41235 both in absolute values. The correlation between the COI and the CAR is strongly positive and it stands at 0.67422 (figure 12)

Changes of correlations through Basel I, II and III

There is no doubt that changes on both qualitative and quantitative level of the calculations of the CAR has had effects on the profitability and COI ratios in the Lebanese

banks. The manifestation of those changes appears in the changes of correlations between variables. Below is an explanation of the correlation changes for each bank across the three phases of the adoption of the Basel recommendations. Period A represents the years of 2004-2006, Period B for the years of 2008-2010 and Period C for the period of 2011-2013 where Basel I, II and III recommendations were respectively adopted in the Lebanese banking sector.

A. Audi Bank

During period A, there was a positive relation between the CAR and ROAA where it stood at 0.998. This correlation has decreased to become insignificant but negative relation where it stood at 0.245 in absolute value. In the period C, this relation increased again but became insignificantly positive where it stood at 0.287. To note that there was a dramatic decrease from period A till period C.

The correlation between the CAR and the ROCE in Period A was positive but insignificant and stood at 0.127 in absolute value. In the second period, there was a dramatic decrease of this correlation since it became strongly negative and stood at 0.993 in absolute value. Another dramatic change occurred during the Period C when this correlation still negative has become insignificant standing at 0.034 in absolute value.

The correlation between the COI and the profitability ratios is negative for the three periods. What varies is the strength of the correlation. In fact the relation between COI and ROAA has changed from being strong in the Period A to insignificant in Period B and finally to strong in the Period C where it stood respectively at 0.963, 0.023 and 0.937.

Concerning the correlation between the COI and the ROCE, the negative relation has increased proportionally in strength across the three periods A, B and C. The correlation was moderate in Period A standing at 0.446 and it increased respectively to 0.943 in Period B and 0.999 in period C.

The correlation between the CAR and the COI had also dramatic changes, while it was strong and negative during Period A, it has increased to become strongly positive in Period B and finally decreased to be insignificantly negative in Period C. On the other side, the COI and CAR correlation respectively stood across Periods A, B and C at 0.944(absolute value), 0.975 and 0.066 (figure 8).

B. BLOM Bank

BLOM bank has also witnessed changes in the correlation between its ratios. To start with the positive strong relation that existed between the CAR and both profitability ratios in Period A that both fluctuated across periods. The correlation between CAR and ROAA stood at 0.979 in period A. it slightly decreased in Period B to remain strongly positive and standing at 0.938. However, in the period C this correlation turned out to be strongly negative and it stood at 0.727 in absolute value. On the other side, the positive correlation between the CAR and the ROCE that stood at 0.728 turned out to be strongly negative in the following period where it stood at 0.992 in absolute value. In period C, the correlation decreased slightly to remain strongly negative and standing at 0.952 in absolute value.

The correlation between COI and ROAA was strongly positive in Period A where it stood at 0.856. It increased till 0.999 in absolute value in period B and then slightly decreased in Period

C to stand at 0.903 in absolute value. The relation between the COI and the ROCE was strongly negative in Period A where it stood at 0.999 in absolute value. It turned out to be strongly positive in the Period B where it stood at 0.976. However; it turned out to be again negatively strongly correlated where it stood at 0.811 in absolute value.

The correlation between the CAR and the COI was strongly negative in the Period A where it stood at 0.733 in absolute value. It increased in the following period to stand at 0.940 in absolute value. The correlation increased to become strongly positive in Period C where it stood at 0.951 (see Figure 9).

C. Byblos Bank

The correlation between the CAR and profitability ratios is positive in the first period. CAR and ROAA are negligibly positively correlated where the correlation stands at 0.343. In period B, the correlation between those variables had increased to become strongly positive standing at 0.987. In the Period C had decreased but remained strong and negative standing at 0.747 in absolute value. Concerning the ROCE, the strong positive correlation in Period A turned out to be moderately negative in Period B and strongly negative in Period C. The correlation between CAR and ROCE stands respectively across Period A, B and C at 0.975, 0.512 and 0.653 in absolute values.

The correlation between COI and profitability ratio is always negative across the years. What changes is the strength of the correlation. In fact, the relation between COI and ROAA was strongly positive in Period A standing at 0.686 in absolute value. This relation became

insignificantly negative in Period B standing at 0.081 in absolute value. The correlation increased in Period C to become strongly negative standing at 0.738.

The CAR and ROCE in Period A were strongly but negatively correlated where the correlation stood at 0.807 in absolute value. This correlation decreased slightly to remain strong and negative standing at 0.712 in absolute value. Another slight decrease characterized Period C; still the correlation remained strong and negative standing at 0.643 in absolute value.

The COI and CAR correlation has also fluctuated. It turned out to be insignificantly negative in Period B while it was strongly negative in Period A. In period C, it increased dramatically in Period C to become strongly positive. The correlations between CAR and COI stand, in absolute values, for Periods A, B and C at 0.919, 0.239 and 0.999 respectively (see Figure 10).

Analysis of the Results

The correlation between variables for the average years of the three banks shows that there is a negative relationship between CAR and Profitability ratios as well as a negative relation between the COI and Profitability ratio. What is notable is that the correlation between variables differs from a bank to the other.

The correlation between the COI and the CAR varies from bank to the other. Where for Byblos for example the COI and CAR are positively highly correlated, they are negligibly positively and negatively correlated for Audi and BLOM bank respectively.

A. Analysis on Ratios for the Total period

a. Audi bank

A decrease in the COI will increase significantly both ROAA and ROCE; but it will not insignificantly decrease the CAR because of the insignificant positive correlation. An increase in the CAR will have insignificant effects on the ROAA and a moderate effect on the ROCE. This means that the CAR of Audi bank is close to its optimal. Even a change in the COI will not have significant effects on the CAR and profitability relationship.

b. BLOM Bank

A decrease in the COI will lead to a significant increase in the ROAA, but to an insignificant decrease in the ROCE. The correlation between the COI and CAR is negligible meaning that a decrease in the COI will not increase the CAR. However, an increase in the CAR for any other reason other than a decrease in the COI will lead to a decrease in the profitability ratio. A decrease in the COI will not have any effects on CAR and that is because of the insignificant correlation between them. The CAR of BLOM bank is also not set at its optimal but at a higher level. Despite the fact that CAR has no double effect on profitability ratio, an increase in the CAR will lead to a decrease in profitability ratio.

c. Byblos Bank

The correlations between variables in the total years for Byblos bank show that a decrease in the COI will lead to an increase in the ROAA as well as in the ROCE. At the same time, it will lead to a decrease in the CAR. A decrease in the CAR will lead to an additional increase in the ROAA and ROCE this ratio relationship explains that the CAR is not set at its

optimal and that is because there is a relationship between CAR and profitability ratios. The current CAR is set above its optimal CAR because a decrease in the CAR will increase bank profitability. An increase in the ROAA will lead to a decrease in the COI that will lead to a decrease in CAR. The decrease in the CAR will lead to an increase in the profitability ratio.

Another thing is that the relation between COI and profitability is always negative. It is strongly negative for all the periods in BLOM Bank and Audi (except for the ROCE in the 2003-2009 period). Concerning Byblos bank, the relation is always moderate (except for the ROAA in the total years)

Analysis on Changes in Correlations

- The relationship between CAR and profitability ratios had decreased for all banks upon shifting to Basel II in 2007 and later upon shifting to Basel III. This relation is always true except for Audi bank upon adoption of Basel III for only the ROAA and for Byblos bank upon adoption of Basel II recommendations. The correlation between CAR and ROCE has always been declining. What can be concluded is that an increase in the CAR will lead to a decrease in the profitability of the Lebanese banks.
- There is always a strong negative correlation between the COI and the profitability ratios except for BLOM bank in the 2008-2010 period with a positive relation between COI and ROCE and Byblos bank has a negative but negligible correlation between COI and ROAA. The negative correlation between COI and profitability ratios means that an increase in the COI will decrease the profitability ratio. The theory of economies of scale is in line with those findings since it says that an

- increase in production (profitability) will lead to an increase in efficiency or to a decrease in cost.
- One notable issue is the change on the level of the correlation between CAR and COI. In fact, there was a strongly negative relation between those two variables in the first period. This relation increased through Basel II and became for both Byblos and BLOM banks strongly positive. Concerning Audi bank, the relation became negligibly positive. A positive correlation between COI and CAR implies that an increase in the CAR will lead to an increase in the COI. This cost is mainly associated to the capital activity raising. Since there is a negative correlation between profitability ratios, a change in the COI will have additional repercussion on profitability.

The decrease in the correlation between CAR and profitability ratios from Basel I capital Accord till Basel II shows that the changes in requirements have had negative repercussion on the profitability in the Lebanese banks. The three CAR for the three banks are not set at their optimal since there is a relationship between CAR and profitability ratios. The change in the correlation's sign between COI and CAR, the decrease in the correlation between CAR and profitability along with the negative correlation between the COI and profitability ratio show that there was a change in the performance and in the interrelation of the variables. What can be concluded is that Lebanese banks are not in line with the pecking order theory and the studies of Berger.

Bank Performance and Scenario Analysis

This section will give the financial explanations of the previously found correlations. It will emphasize the effects of changes in the CAR and COI on the profitability ratios in the three periods and it will project those findings on future increase in the CAR as well as COI.

a. Audi Bank

The correlation between variable during 2004-2006 show that an increase in the CAR will lead to an increase in the ROAA and a slight increase in the ROCE. The increase in the profitability ratio will lead to a decrease in the COI. At the same time, the decrease in the CAR will lead to a decrease in the COI. This will lead to an additional increase in the ROAA. According to Berger, the CAR of Audi during this period was set below its optimal CAR since an increase in the CAR has led to an increase in the profitability ratio. IF the bank in this case increases its CAR, this will allow him to build future additional capital from profits. After a period of time, it will get to its optimal CAR because the bank is building its capital from profits which are thought to have the lowest cost of funding. This is shown in the intersection of the ROCE and the CAR in the 2008.

In the period of 2008-2010, a decrease in the CAR will lead to an increase in the profitability ratios. This means that the CAR is set at level above its optimal. The increase in the profitability ratio will lead to a decrease in the COI. This is true in particular for the ROCE because of the strong positive correlation. In addition, a decrease in the CAR will lead to an additional decrease in the COI, a decrease in the COI will lead to an additional increase in the profitability ratios. The same conclusion for the first period would be also correct where the bank

will be able to build up its capital because of an increase in the profitability ratios. Banks will eventually get to their optimal CAR. In this case, this optimal CAR is almost achieved for bank Audi in the 2013.

A decrease in the COI will lead to an increase in the profitability ratios. However; the CAR will not be affected by any changes in COI, ROA and ROE because of the negligible relation between CAR and the previously mentioned variables. However; according to the pecking order theory if there was an increase in the CAR for following periods, the correlations will change. An increase in the CAR will lead to a decrease in the profitability ratios leading to an increase in the COI.

b. BLOM Bank

In the period of the 2004-2006, the correlations indicate that an increase in the CAR will lead to an increase in the profitability ratios. This means that the CAR is set at a level below its optimal CAR. The increase in the CAR will lead to an increase in the profitability ratios and to a decrease in the COI at the same time. This will lead to an additional increase in the profitability. The bank will continue until it reaches its equilibrium or optimal CAR level. The intersection point for BLOM bank was between the year 2008 and 2009.

What is notable for BLOM bank is the positive relation between the COI and ROCE and the negative relation between the CAR and the ROCE. On the other hand, there is a positive relation between the ROAA and CAR but a negative relation between COI and ROAA.

The 2011-2013 correlations show that an increase in the CAR will lead to a reduction in both profitability ratios as well as an increase in the COI. The increase in the COI will lead to an additional decrease in the profitability ratios. At this time, BLOM bank will have to find other ways in order for it to increase its capital this will lead to a higher COI and an additional decrease in the profitability ratio. In this case, this scenario will not be in line with the pecking order theory. In contrast; the actual CAR should be decreased and that is due to the previously mentioned repercussions a high CAR can have on a bank. Those repercussions include inducing pro cyclical effects, increasing risk and decreasing loans.

What shall be done instead is to decrease the CAR. A decrease in the CAR will lead to a decrease in the COI especially in the cost associated for capital rising. This will also lead to an increase in the profitability ratio that will lower the COI leading to a lower optimal CAR. To note that even a decrease in the COI associated with capital fund will lead to an increase in the profitability because this will lower the overall cost per transaction and thus automatically increase profitability.

c. Byblos Bank

The analysis of the 2011-2013 period of Byblos bank also shows that an increase in the CAR will decrease profitability but increase COI. This is also shown in the graphs (Figure 5 and 9) as well as in table 3. The COI increase is as result related to cost of raising fund so the cost associated with production will not increase meaning that the profitability will not increase. The cost of income related to build the capital will have negative repercussion on profitability.

What shall be done in this case, as an alternative for decreasing CAR. For both BLOM and Byblos banks is to find other ways to increase profitability. Especially for Byblos Bank, this is true because Byblos holds a very high COI but very low profitability ratios. Still it holds a moderate CAR when compared to other banks but a higher CAR than its optimal.

An increase in the profitability will lead to a decrease in the CAR as well as in the COI. At this time the decrease in COI is the cost associated with production and this is true due to the theory of economies of scale. In the same time, the bank would be able to decrease the cost associated to raising capital because it can build its capital from profits which are the cheapest funds. This will lead to a decrease in the optimal CAR since more profitable banks have lower optimal CAR. As shown in the three graphs for the three banks, the two lines of CAR and ROCE will eventually intersect. The lower the COI used to generate profit, the lower is the optimal CAR the higher are the profits and the lower is the cost of generating capital

This is also shown in the graphs where BLOM bank has the highest profitability ratios and the lowest COI. At the same time, the previous analysis has shown that BLOM bank holds a higher CAR than it should. This is true especially for the period before the 2008. After this period, BLOM bank kept a relatively high CAR. This is in line with the findings more profitable banks can keep lower CAR. An increase in the CAR will as consequence decrease bank profitability.

Audi holds a relatively high COI with a low CAR. At the same time it holds average profitability ratios when compared to the other banks. To note, that the correlation between the COI and the CAR in the period of 2011-2013 is negligible (Table 3). This means

that the high COI is exclusively associated with production. Audi bank should decrease its COI. This step will only have effects on profitability but not on the CAR.

The previous analysis shows that BLOM and Byblos banks hold a higher CAR more than they should do. Audi bank is close to its optimal CAR. In the three cases, an additional increase in the CAR will lead to a decrease in the profitability. On the other side, a decrease in the COI will lead to an increase in the profitability ratios. This will lead the CAR to an optimal level. Once reached there will be an insignificant correlation between CAR and Profitability ratios and an insignificant relation between COI and CAR which is the case of Audi in the 2011-2013 period.

Optimal Capital Adequacy Ratio

According to Osborne, an optimal CAR will not have any effects on the profitability of banks. As concluded before, Audi bank is the closest to the optimal CAR. This can be shown especially in the 2011-2013 period. Where there is a negligible relationship between CAR and profitability ratio. What is also noted the negligible relation between the CAR and the COI. The increase in the CAR will not affect the COI. The explanation behind this fact is that Audi bank raises its capital from past profit and in periods of high cash excess as well as from owner's equity. This is what explains the high correlation between COI and ROAA and ROCE.

Another thing is the strong negative relationship between COI and profitability ratio. A decrease in the COI at this time will only increase the ROA and ROE without having any other indirect changes on those ratios since it will not affect the CAR. To note that in terms of ratios, Audi bank holds the lowest CAR for the same period if compared to BLOM bank and Byblos

bank. This means that a high CAR is not always the optimal CAR. A decrease in the COI will increase bank profitability. The degree of this increase depends on the correlation between COI and the profitability ratio.

A decrease in the CAR and decrease in the COI will both increase the profitability ratios as long as there is a positive relationship between COI and CAR and a negative relation between CAR and profitability ratio. Where, the positive relationship between CAR and COI implies that an increase in the CAR will lead to an increase in the cost associated with raising the capital. The positive correlation was found in the period of 2011-2013. This could be due to the burden of meeting Basel III requirements. Especially that Basel III has implemented changes on both quantitative and qualitative levels of the CAR

In this case, which is BLOM and Byblos bank case, the banks will reach their optimal CAR by using other means to increase profitability, decrease COI or decrease CAR. The three means will have the same end result and this is due to the way they are correlated. An increased profitability will lead the COI to decrease. A decrease in the COI will lead The CAR to decrease. A decrease in the CAR will lead to an increase in the ROAA that will keep on lowering both COI and CAR until CAR reaches its optimal. This is in line with what was previously discussed that the current CAR of BLOM and Byblos bank are set at a higher level than their optimal CAR. To note that a high cost of capital rising is one of the major components that affect the CAR profitability relationship

The above-mentioned scenarios are true when a positive correlation exists between the CAR and COI and a negative relation exist between CAR and Profitability ratios.

If the correlation was positive between CAR and COI as well between CAR and profitability ratios, a decrease in the COI and an increase in the CAR will perform in the same way to meet the pecking order and trade off theories will be true, an increase in the CAR will lead to a decrease in the COI thus to an increase in the profitability.

While a negative correlation between COI and CAR and a positive relation between CAR and profitability ratio means that a decrease in the COI will lead to an increase in the CAR which assures that the capital raised by profits is less costly than the other means of raising capital and that is because of the negative relationship between COI and profitability ratios. This is what was explained in the case of BLOM for the period of 2004-2006 (Table 2). The CAR will get to an optimal where it offset the cost and benefits of raising capital.

The tables 1, 2 and 3 show that before Basel II all banks had very high CAR when compared to the CAR after Basel II adoption. The decrease in the ratios could be explained by the new restrictions that Basel II has implemented. Another thing is that the CAR of all banks in the 2008, when Lebanese banks started to adopt Basel II recommendations, was approximately the same. In the consolidated balance sheet of Byblos Bank, the CAR for example for the year 2009 was 22.13% if it was calculated based on Basel I calculations. The same ratio turned out to be 12.62% if calculated based on Basel II.

The study conducted by the IMF that concluded that CAR are not comparable across countries, can be projected on the Lebanese market to shed the light about this issue. For the same potential losses coming from different risk absorbing, bank resiliency and limiting pro cyclical effects, the CAR is having two different values. Another thing is that in the Lebanese

banks, different approaches are allowed to be used in CAR calculations which will be an additional reason to increase in the ambiguity and reliability of the ability of CAR to reflect a true bank capitalization. However; what was used in this study was the correlation between variables that measures the effects of changes of one variable on the other variable. That is why the optimal CAR and the changes of the current CAR cannot be exactly tracked.

The CAR for Audi bank is the lowest when compared to Byblos and BLOM banks. This approves the fact that a high CAR is not always optimal. A notable point is that there is an intersection point between the CAR line and the ROE line. The ROCE varies from 13.3 in the 2008 till 13.6 in the 2013. The same is true for the CAR that varies from 12.84% in the 2008 till 12.9% in the 2013. That is what explains the negligible correlation between those two variables.

In addition, the study of Berger assures the findings that the CAR of the Lebanese banks are set at a level above their optimal, a decrease in the CAR will lead to an increase in the profitability of the bank instead. An increase in the profitability ratios will decrease in the COI that will in return increase ROAA and ROCE. The level of the CAR will reach to an optimal level where it offset the cost and the benefits of raising capital. The time length to get to the optimal CAR varies depends on the current CAR and how far it stands from its optimal in addition to the signs and strength of correlations between the variables.

As previously shown, an increase in the CAR for the three banks will lead to a decrease in the profitability ratios. On the other hand, after we consulted a group of qualified consulting financial key personnel mainly selected form the top alpha banks in Lebanon, we took their remarks recommendations and analysis on the subject of an increase in the CAR.

After conducting the F2F interviews each lasting around 40 to 50 minutes we concluded our main findings after comparing, modulating and assessing each answer to as to build up the following assumptions:

According to the consulting group we have interviewed, banks have different alternatives on how to respond to the challenges the regulation imposes. Through these different approaches the management of a bank can choose which risks are worth taking and which opportunities might arise as a result.

The importance of the minimal CAR the BCBS and the BDL have given, has urged Lebanese banks to meet the requirements. The main reason behind this is to give a security for both investors and depositor. However; the analysis of the financial ratios of Alpha banks show that there has always been a variation in the CAR but the deposit has been increasing but at a different growth ratio. Deposits and external deposits are related to financial and political stability more into the level of CAR. It is also related to the strength of the industry of the investment.

To note, that the banking industry is one of the most resilient industries in Lebanon and one of the important sectors in the MENA region. There are many reasons behind the resiliency among them; we can mention the Lebanese banking secrecy, the governor of BDL by himself and the transparency of the banks through their financial statements.

The cost to increase income can be used to increase profitability instead. Banks can expand their market share by introducing new products to the market, open new operating branches and expand their green marketing campaign. Green marketing campaigns can contribute the increase the welfare of the overall society. Banks can also decrease their COI making the banking sector a more efficient one. A decrease in the COI will also increase the

bank competitiveness. This would be reflected in the decrease of the fees the bank imposes on their clients. This will lead to an additional increase in their market share. To note that Audi bank has the highest fee; that's what explains the reason behind a high COI and a relative high profitability.

Despite the fact that loans are increasing at an increasing growth rate, we can notice that profitability is not increasing accordingly. There are many reasons behind this bank's performance. Bank's inefficiency could be one major reason. BLOM bank when compared to other banks has the lowest COI but the highest CAR.

An increase in the profitability will lead to a decrease in the COI and that is because of the theory of the economies of scale. In fact, an increase in the profitability is another way around to decrease COI. The increase of loans is an opportunity to increase bank's profitability. There are other ways to boost profitability such as a better management of already existing assets.

Raising the quality of employees through a better recruitment and ongoing training systems could be one effective way to increase profitability. Banks can also adopt more innovative Customer Relationship Management programs. Those programs can enhance the relation between the bank and its clients. Least but last, banks should try to decrease the Non-performing loans rate. This could be because of an increase in the moral hazard of the employees. Instead credit scoring system can systematically, scientifically and objectively assess loans candidate files.

On the other side, a paradoxical issue occurs. Banks should maintain the equilibrium between the loan size and the profitability. High loans with high excessive returns can lead to a bubble burst the same as happened in the 2008 financial crisis in the USA. On the other hand, excessive loans with low profitability can lead banks to go bankrupt in the long term. The Lebanese market had witnessed many mergers and acquisitions. Mergers and acquisitions can be an effective tool in preventing from a bank going bankrupt. A bankruptcy of a certain bank in a certain market can lead to a loss in the trust given to the whole banking sector. As a result, successive bankruptcy might follow.

Other tools to prevent from a probable financial crisis in the Lebanese market are the strict policy of the BDL and the timing of building the optimal CAR. In fact, the reserves held at BDL by each bank would be used in case of any run occurrence. Another thing is the insurance the BDL gives to banks in case of a probable run occurrence. In addition, the BDL strictly recommends banks to invest in relative short-term liquid marketable securities. The CAR should be built at periods of high growth rate of profitability. At that time, the CAR would be one tool to prevent from a financial crisis.

Lebanon exposure to external investment is also regulated by the BDL. Exposure to financial markets and high leverage ratios are two main reasons for a financial crisis. The risk the Lebanese market is exposed to is not enough to lead to a financial crisis in the Lebanese market.

CHAPTER 5

CONCLUSION

To conclude, the Lebanese market sector is one of the most resilient industries in Lebanon and in the MENA region. Even though, the worldwide financial sector was affected by the 2008 financial crisis, Lebanese banks stood relatively unaffected. However, the Lebanese market is witnessing a current challenging political as well as economic situation. Those challenges were reflected by a slower increase in the Lebanese profitability ratios when compared to previous years.

There is a tight relationship between CAR, COI and profitability ratios. The study above proved that an increase in the CAR will lead to a decrease in the profitability of the three banks stressing the point that the alpha banks hold the lowest CAR when compared to the other segments of the Lebanese banking industry. As a result, an increase in the overall CAR will lead, in the long term, to unprofitable banking industry.

Every bank, should find its optimal CAR. A certain CAR is set at its optimal when there is no correlation between the previously mentioned variables. At this time, the cost of raising

capital will offset the benefits of the CAR. This will maintain a resilient, profitable and efficient Lebanese banking sector.

This study was conducting excluding any other variables that might affect profitability except for CAR. The results have shown that high CAR does not prevent from future financial crises; instead, it might have repercussions on the macroeconomic level and on the financial sector specially. Banks should not be placed under constraints of increasing CAR and at paying high opportunity costs. This study will open new questions such as the real causes of financial and economical collapses. The final concern remains. Is a high CAR a burden created and a tool used to manipulate the occurrence of financial crises and to contribute to a macroeconomic collapse?

Recommendations

The profitability of the three banks has decreased after the adoption of Basel II, in the 2014 the Lebanese banks will start to adopt the Basel III. The adoption of Basel III could induce banks to bear higher cost of raising capitals. The marginal decrease in the correlation between CAR and profitability ratio could increase after the adoption of Basel. Especially that the correlation between those variables is negative. An increase in the CAR will keep on decreasing the profitability ratio to decrease. Per consequence, the COI will increase. By this, the capital adequacy ratio will increase higher than its optimal. The procedure will not be in line with the pecking order theory. Banks will suffer from profitability problems. Since profitability is one key element of the existence of any industry.

It is not necessary for the Lebanese banking sector to abide by Basel III regulations. Low growth in return is an additional reason for bank not to go for a high CAR. An optimal CAR should be set for each bank and that is based on the strategy of the bank. The capital adequacy ratio will perform at its best at this time. It will be able to absorb losses, make the banking sector a resilient sector and provide counter cyclical effects. It will not affect the bank profitability. And thus, will not increase the bankruptcy risk.

On the other hand, the same components of the CAR as well as the models used to calculate the risk in the formula should be adopted and that is to make the CAR comparable across the banks in the Lebanese banking sector.

If the BDL implemented to adopt the CAR as per Basel recommendations, Lebanese banks should find ways to decrease the COI since a decrease in the COI will boost profits. Banks can build capital from those earnings. By this, the COI will decrease and that is because of the economy of scales and the lower cost per transaction cost.

Banks can also find other ways to increase profitability other than decreasing cost. Eventually, high profits will decrease COI that will also result in higher earnings. By that time, the financial sector will be characterized by a period of high growth excess. This is when the capital should be built up. And that is because of the low cost of rising them and because higher CAR would decrease the repercussions of high money supply in the market. To note that, the Lebanese banking sector is not witnessing an excessive period of excessive growth rate.

APPENDIX A

Figure 1:

Source: Parc Lebanon, Audi CAR, COI, ROCE, ROAA

Figure 2:

Source: Parc Lebanon, Byblos Bank CAR, COI, ROCE, ROAA

Figure 3

Source: Parc Lebanon, BLOM Bank CAR, COI, ROCE, ROAA

Figure 4

Source: Parc Lebanon, CAR Trend for Audi, Byblos and BLOM banks 2004-2013

Figure 5

Figure 6

Source: Parc Lebanon, ROAA for Audi, Byblos and BLOM banks; 2004-2013

Figure 7

Source: Parc Lebanon, ROCE for Audi, Byblos and BLOM banks; 2004-2013

	OI	CAR/C	CAR/	CAR	COI/R	COI/
			ROCE	/ROAA	OCE	ROAA
Audi		-		0.998		
Basel I		0.944	0.127		-0.446	-0.963
				-		
Basel II		0.975	-0.993	0.245	-0.943	-0.023
Basel III		0.066	-0.034	- 0.287	-0.999	-0.937
Total		0.378	-0.520	-0.699	-0.845	-0.699

Table 1

Source: Parc Lebanon, Audi Bank Correlation Table

	OI	CAR/C	CAR	CAR	COI/	COI/
			/ROCE	/ROAA	ROCE	ROAA
BLOM				0.979		
Basel I	0.733	-	0.728	0.938	0.856	0.856
Basel II	0.941	-	0.992	-0.727	0.976	0.999
Basel III		0.951	-0.952	-0.598	-0.810	-0.903
Total						
Period		-0.051	-0.650		-0.244	-0.673

Table 2

Source: Parc Lebanon, BLOM Bank Correlation

blom	-		0.3	-	-	
Basel I	0.919		0.975	43	0.807	0.686
	-	-	0.9		-	-
Basel II	0.239	0.512	87		0.712	0.081
			-0.747			-
Basel III	0.999	-0.653			-0.643	0.738
Total			-0.689			-
Period	0.674	-0.523			-0.412	0.682

Table 3

Source: Parc Lebanon, Byblos Bank Correlation Table

APPENDIX B

Questions for Qualitative Analysis

- Do you think that Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) negatively affect the profitability? Why?
 1. The loan and advance are at an increasing path in the Lebanese sector; however the profitability ratios are not increasing accordingly. Taking into consideration the fact that loans are the main bank's activity, what are the reasons that prohibit the increase of profitability ratio?
 2. What do you think are the reasons behind the differences in correlations between the variables across the banks
 3. Why did the correlations between variables decreased after adoption of Basel III
 4. Do you think the adoption of Basel III implementation will have additional repercussion on profitability of banks?
 5. If banks decrease their Cost of Income, will they increase their profitability?
 6. What are the other ways to increase profitability?
 7. If the BDL did not recommend for Lebanese banks to abide by Basel III recommendations and if it decided to decrease the minimum required Capital adequacy ratio. Will this affect customer/foreign investor's behavior?
 8. Even though Lebanon is considered to have a resilient banking sector, would be at a risk of facing a financial crisis because slow growth in returns and high CAR?

REFERENCES

- Allessi, S. (2012): The Basel Committee on Banking Supervision, Council on Foreign Relation
- Andrieş, A. M. (2009). What role have banks in financial crises? *Review of Economic and Business Studies (REBS)*, (3), 149-159.
- Auer, M., & von Pfoesti, G. (2012). Basel III Handbook.
- Arthur, D. Little (2008): Five Habits of Highly Efficient Banks. How Banks Ride the Cost-income Curve, August 8.
- Association of Banks in Lebanon. (2011, June 30). Lebanese Banking Sector. Website: www.abl.org.lb
- Beccalli, E., Casu, B., & Girardone, C. (2006). Efficiency and stock performance in European banking. *Journal of Business Finance & Accounting*, 33(1-2), 245-262.
- Bentum, W. (2012). The Determinants of Profitability of the Commercial Banks in Ghana during the Recent Years of Global Financial Crisis.
- Balthazar, L. (2006). From Basel 1 to Basel 3. Palgrave Macmillan
- Basel Committee on Banking Supervision (2013): A Brief History of the Basel Committee
- Basel Committee on Banking Supervision (2011): Basel III: A global regulatory framework for more resilient banks and banking systems
- Besanko, D., & Spulber, D. F. (1989). Antitrust enforcement under asymmetric information. *The Economic Journal*, 408-425
- Barakat M. S., Naayem J. H., & Kanso A. F. (2014). Lebanon Banking Sector Report: Bank Audi Sector Research
- Barrell, R., & Gottschalk, S. (2006). The impacts of capital adequacy requirements on emerging markets. National Institute of Economic and Social Research.
- Basel Committee. (2010). Basel III: A global regulatory framework for more resilient banks and banking systems. *Basel Committee on Banking Supervision, Basel*.

- Basel Committee on Banking Supervision, & Bank for International Settlements. (2004). *International convergence of capital standards: a revised framework*. Lulu. Com
- Banque du Liban. (2014, July 03). Circular N 358: Capital Adequacy
- Berger, A. N., & Udell, G. F. (2004). The institutional memory hypothesis and the procyclicality of bank Hölmstrom, B. (1979). Moral hazard and observability. *The Bell Journal of Economics*, 74-91.
- Baer, H. L., & McElravey, J. (1992). *Capital adequacy and the growth of US banks* (No. 92-11). Federal Reserve Bank of Chicago.
- Basel's Capital Curse by Steve H. Hanke, January 2013 issue of *Globe Asia*
- Cecchetti, S. G., Kohler, M., & Upper, C. (2009). *Financial crises and economic activity* (No. w15379). National Bureau of Economic Research
- Covas, F., & Fujita, S. (2010). Procyclicality of capital requirements in a general equilibrium model of liquidity dependence. *International Journal of Central Banking*, 6(4), 137-173.
- Daianu, D., & Lungu, L. (2008). Why is this financial crisis occurring? How to respond to it. *Romanian Journal of Economic Forecasting*, 4, 59-87.
- Elizalde, A., & Repullo, R. (2007). Economic and regulatory capital in banking: What is the difference? *International Journal of Central Banking*, 3(3), 87-117.
- Flamini, V., Schumacher, L., & McDonald, C. A. (2009). *The determinants of commercial bank profitability in Sub-Saharan Africa*. International Monetary Fund.
- Gorton, G., & Winton, A. (2003). Financial intermediation. *Handbook of the Economics of Finance*, 1, 431-552
- Gambacorta, L., Yang, J., & Tsatsaronis, K. (2014). Financial structure and growth. *International banking and financial market developments*, 3, 21.
- Hanke, S. H. (2012). *Basel's Capital Curse*.
- Investment Development Authority of Lebanon. Financial System Overview. Retrieved from: http://investinlebanon.gov.lb/Content/uploads/SideBlock/130130020544957~Financing_your_Business-_Financial_System_Overview.pdf

- Kock, S. (1995). Implementation considerations for activity-based cost systems in service firms: the unavoidable challenge. *Management Decision*, 33(6), 57-63.
- Koehn, M., & Santomero, A. M. (1980). Regulation of bank capital and portfolio risk. *The journal of finance*, 35(5), 1235-1244.
- Laeven, L., & Levine, R. (2009). Bank governance, regulation and risk taking. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 93(2), 259-275.
- Lekatis, G. (2011): Basel III: Understanding the Capital Conservation Buffer, Treasury
- Landau, J. P. (2009, May). Procyclicality: what it means and what could be done. In *remarks at the Bank of Spain's conference on Procyclicality and the Role of Financial Regulation, Madrid, May*.
- Lending Behavior. *Journal of financial intermediation*, 13(4), 458-495.
- Lin, Y. H. Optimal Bank Regulation in an Economic Boom and Recession.
- Le Leslé, V., & Avramova, S. (2012). Revisiting risk-weighted assets. International monetary fund (IMF)
- Laughlin, R. J. (1990). Causes of the Savings and Loan Debacle. *Fordham L. Rev.* S301, 59
- Molyneux, P., Altunbas, Y., & Gardener, E. P. (1996). Efficiency in European banking. Chichester: Wiley.
- Mili, M., Sahut, J. M., & Trimeche, H. (2014). Determinants of the Capital Adequacy Ratio of a Foreign Bank's Subsidiaries: Banks'2012 growth hinges on regional changes The Role of the Interbank Market and Regulation of Multinational Banks (No. 2014-366).
- Mathuva, D. M. (2009). Capital adequacy, cost income ratio and the performance of commercial banks: The Kenyan Scenario. *The International Journal of Applied Economics and Finance*, 3(2), 35-47.
- Nehme. R. (2011). Handbook of Lebanese Financial Regulations
- OSBORNE, M., FUERTES, A. M., & MILNE, A. Capital and profitability in banking: Evidence from US banks.
- Olweny, T., & Shipho, T. M. (2011). Effects of banking sectoral factors on the profitability of commercial banks in Kenya. *Economics and Finance Review*, 1(5), 1-30.
- Packer, F., & Zhu, H. (2012). Loan loss provisioning practices of Asian banks.

- Pancurova, D., & Lyocsa, S. (2013). Determinants of commercial banks' efficiency: evidence from 11 CEE Countries. *Czech Journal of Economics and Finance (Finance a uver)*, 63(2), 152-179.
- Reserve Bank of New Zealand. (2007, July 17). Capital adequacy ratio for banks-simplified explanation and example of calculation. Retrieved from http://people.stern.nyu.edu/igiddy/articles/capital_adequacy_calculation.pdf
- Repullo, R., & Saurina Salas, J. (2011). The countercyclical capital buffer of Basel III: A critical assessment.
- Smiley, G. (2008). *The concise encyclopedia of economics: great depression*.
- Sakr, E. (2011). Banks' 2012 growth hinges on regional changes, the daily star
- Trehan, R. (2008). *Market-based finance vs. bank-based finance*, Credit Capital Funding
- Thun, C. (2011): *Introduction to Basel Regulation and Credit Risk Modeling*, Moody's Analytics
- Times, F. (2012). *Financial Times Lexicon*. Retrieved December, 31, 2012
- Tripe, D. (1998). Cost to income ratios in Australasian banking. Department of Finance, Banking and Property, College of Business, Massey University.
- Winter Söderberg, C., & Göransson, S. (2011). *THE BANK CRISIS FINANCIAL RATIOS: A comparative research of the UK and Sweden during 2006-2010*.
- Yoshino, N., Hirano, T., & Miura, K. (2009). The optimal Basel capital requirement to cope with pro-cyclicality: A theoretical approach. Financial Services Agency, Government of Japan.
- Yoshino, N., Hirano, T., & Miura, K. (2009). The optimal Basel capital requirement to cope with pro-cyclicality: A theoretical approach. Financial Services Agency, Government of Japan.
- Yoshino, N., Hirano, T., & Miura, K. (2009). The optimal Basel capital requirement to cope with pro-cyclicality: A theoretical approach. Financial Services Agency, Government of Japan.

